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Topographic Influences on GNSS Jamming Signals: A Simulation Study in Finland

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Abstract			
<p>Satellite positioning is vulnerable to interference due to the power of satellite signals. Satellite signals are exceptionally weak when they arrive to the Earth and therefore susceptible to radio frequency interference (RFI). This makes even low-power interference effective, possibly for radius of several kilometers. Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) services, such as positioning, navigation and timing services (PNT), are widely used among our society by civilians and authorities. Critical infrastructures, such as money transfer and electricity transmission networks, rely on accurate timing data provided by GNSS's atomic clocks. These services are under a serious threat by RFI —intentionally created or not. In the areas that GNSS jamming signal can cover, the PNT services are most likely degraded or entirely unavailable. The easiest way to intentionally create RFI is to create jamming interference by broadcasting empty signal on satellite signal frequency with simple jamming radio devices aka jammers. Jammers disturb GNSS services by blocking entire positioning data or deteriorating positioning accuracy which leads to inaccurate location information.</p> <p>Jamming is an emerging global threat for GNSS services since jammers can be easily bought online, even though jamming is illegal in Europe and many other regions. Incentives for jamming differ by the user group of jamming equipment. Civilian jamming is mostly done with low-power jammers for protecting privacy by hiding location information and it is normally done without further knowledge about the effects for the surrounding environment. The more severe threat is done with high-power jamming equipment by professionals. This kind of interference has motives for either disturbance or denial of GNSS services or to defend against different location-based measures. Jamming and RFI are significant parts of electronic warfare.</p> <p>This study tested the usability of MATLAB's RF Toolbox on simulating jamming signals horizontally in different topographies across Finland to demonstrate how spatially effective jamming actually is. Used jamming signals were simulated with four different powers on Galileo's E1 and GPS's L1 signal (1575.42 MHz) to exemplify the effects of different power interference. The simulations and inspection of signal propagation were done with MATLAB by visualizing the expected power of jamming signal and calculating propagation loss for receiver matrix above digital elevation model (DEM). The used method was not able to calculate propagation values for varying power and exact values for signal attenuation of jamming signal cannot be calculated with MATLAB. RFI is illegal in Finland, therefore field work is not possible for this kind of study.</p> <p>This study highlights the hindering or blocking effect of topography on jamming signal propagation alongside with the effectiveness of different jammer power levels. Signals obey signal propagation models, but topographic characteristics, such as hills, have an ability to hinder the propagation. The results emphasize the spatial effects of even low-power jammers that are used by civilians and accentuates the significance of topography to signal propagation. Effective jamming over different topographic characteristics can be conducted with even 500 mW jammer and increase of jammer power is able to cover extensive areas of irregular terrain. The most vulnerable areas to GNSS jamming are open, unbuilt areas. However, the impact of locally bounded urban jamming scenario is also severe to the population and infrastructures of the area.</p>			
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Tiivistelmä <p>Satelliittisignaalit ovat äärimmäisen heikkoja saapuessaan Maan pinnalle, mikä tekee ne alttiiksi radiotaajuushäirinnälle. Jo matalatehoinen häirintä on tehokasta jopa kilometrien säteellä. GNSS-palvelut (Global Navigation Satellite System, kansainvälinen satelliittipaikannusjärjestelmä), kuten paikannus-, navigointi- ja aikatietopalvelut, ovat laajalti käytettyjä palveluja yhteiskunnassamme niin siviili- kuin viranomaiskäyttäjien toimesta. Kriittiset infrastruktuurit, kuten sähkönsiirtoverkko, ovat riippuvaisia satelliittien atomikellojen tuottamasta tarkasta aikatiedosta. GNSS-palvelut ovat uhattuina radiotaajuushäirinnän vuoksi, oli häirintä tahallisesti tuotettua tai ei. Häiriöalueilla paikannus-, navigointi- ja aikatietopalvelujen käyttö on kokonaan estetty tai niiden tuottama tieto on heikkolaatuista. Helpoimmin häirintää tehdään lähettämällä tyhjää signaalia satelliittisignaalin taajuudella yksinkertaisilla radiolähettimillä, eli niin sanotuilla jammereilla. Jammerit aiheuttavat häiriöitä GNSS-palveluille joko estämällä paikannusdatan vastaanottamisen tai heikentämällä saavutettua paikannustarkkuutta, joka johtaa virheelliseen sijaintitietoon.</p> <p>Satelliittipaikannuksen häirintä, eritoten niin kutsuttu jamming, on globaalisti kasvava uhka GNSS-palveluille, koska jammereita voidaan helposti ostaa verkosta, vaikkakin häirintä on laitonta toimintaa Euroopassa ja muilla alueilla. Häiritsemiselle on useita käyttäjäryhmästä riippuvaisia kannustimia. Siviilien tekemä häirintä tehdään yleensä oman sijaintitiedon peittämiseksi matalatehoisilla häirintälaitteilla, eikä siviilikäyttäjillä yleensä ole tietoa häirinnän alueellisista vaikutuksista. Vakavalaatuisinta häirintää saadaan aikaan tehokkailla ammattilaislaitteilla. Tehokasta häirintää tehdään tahallisesti, jotta GNSS-palvelujen käyttöä saataisiin vaikeutettua ja mahdollisesti estettyä tai jotta voitaisiin puolustautua sijaintietoon perustuvilta toimilta. Radiotaajuuksien häirintää hyödynnetään elektronisessa sodankäynnissä.</p> <p>Tämä tutkielma tarkastelee MATLAB:in RF Toolbox -työkalupakin käytettävyyttä häirintäsignaalin horisontaaliseen mallinnukseen erilaisten pinnanmuotojen päällä sekä häirinnän alueellisen vaikutuksen tarkasteluun. Häirintäsignaaleja simuloidaan neljällä eri teholla Galileon E1- ja GPS:n L1-taajuuksille (1575.42 MHz), jotta voidaan ilmentää eri tehoisten häiriöiden vaikutuksia. Simulaatiot ja signaalin häviön tarkastelu tehtiin MATLAB:illa visualisoiden odotetun häirintäsignaalin tehoa sekä laskemalla signaalin häviö signaalivastaanotinmatriisilla, joka oli mallinnettu korkeusmallin päälle. MATLABin metodeilla ei voitu laskea signaalin häviön määrää, kun häirinnän teho muuttui, eli metodi ei sovi tarkkojen arvojen laskemiseen vaan ennemminkin signaalin häviön laskemiseen etäisyyden funktiona. Radiotaajuuksien häirintä on laitonta Suomessa, joten tutkimuksen tekeminen oikeassa ympäristössä kenttätöyönä ei ole mahdollista.</p> <p>Tutkimustulokset korostavat pinnanmuotojen häiriösignaalien estävää tai vähentävää merkitystä häiriön leviämisenle. Signaalit käyttäytyvät signaalien häviömallien mukaisesti, mutta pinnanmuodot, kuten tunturit ja kukkulat, voivat estää häirintäsignaalin leviämistä. Tutkimustulokset myös alleviivaavat jo matalatehoisten siviilien käyttämien häirintälaitteiden aiheuttaman häiriön alueellista merkitystä sekä korostavat pinnanmuotojen vaikutusta häirintäsignaalin leviämisenle. Alueita voidaan tehokkaasti häiritä jopa 500 milliwatin tehoisilla häirintälaitteilla, jotka kykenevät tuottamaan laajan häiriön jopa epätasaisessa maastossa. Avoimet, rakentamattomat alueet ovat haavoittuvaisimpia häirintäsignaaleille. Rakennetuilla kaupunkialueilla häirintäsignaalin kulkua estää topografian lisäksi rakennukset rajoittaen häiriöalueen pienelle alueelle. Kaupunkialueet ovat kuitenkin haavoittuvaisia häirinnälle alueen väestön ja infrastruktuurien suhteen.</p>			
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ABBREVIATIONS

BDS	the BeiDou Navigation Satellite System (北斗卫星导航系统 in Chinese)
dB	Decibel
dBm	Decibel-milliwatt
DEM	Digital elevation model
ESA	the European Space Agency
EW	Electronic warfare
GHz	Gigahertz
GLONASS	the GLObal Navigation Satellite System (Глобальная навигационная спутниковая система in Russian)
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	the Global Positioning System
HAS	the High Accuracy Service
LOS	Line-of-Sight
MHz	Megahertz
mW	Milliwatt
NLS	the National Land Survey of Finland
PPP	Precise point positioning
PNT	Position, navigation and timing
PDOP	Position dilution of precision
RF	Radio frequency
RFI	Radio frequency interference
SBAS	Satellite-based augmentation systems
W	Watt

1 INTRODUCTION

Global Navigation Satellite System, GNSS, is defined as selection of satellite navigation systems and their augmentations (Kaplan, 2017). GNSS services, such as positioning, navigation and timing services (PNT), are widely used among our society by civilians and authorities. We use PNT services in our everyday life to navigate and to synchronize the timing of bank transactions. These services are under a serious threat by radio frequency interference (RFI) —intentionally created or not (Elango et al., 2022a). Critical infrastructures, such as money transfer, rely on accurate timing data provided by GNSS's atomic clocks.

GNSS services, especially satellite positioning, are vulnerable for interference due to the low power of signals from the navigation satellites that reach the surface of the Earth. Satellite signals are exceptionally weak, typically around -130 dBm, as they travel from satellites orbiting at approximately 20 000 kilometers in space (Elango et al., 2022a; Spirent 2018; OS SIS ICD, 2023). The power of a satellite signal is sometimes compared to the power of a light bulb located thousands of kilometers from the viewer. Due to their low strength, satellite signals are susceptible to RFI. This susceptibility is an incentive for RFI (Margaria & Pini, 2015).

Interference can be created intentionally or unintentionally. Intentional interference is made deliberately with some end-goal in mind, such as interfering the location services. Unintentional interference on the other hand can arise from various factors such as rough topography of the area in concern, which can result in multipath signals. Multipath signals can also be formed when signals journey is disrupted by e. g. obstacles such as buildings or trees.

Jamming is a form of radio frequency interference where radio frequency energy is intentionally transmitted as a false satellite signal to block or hinder navigation services (Dovis, 2015; Miljanovic et al., 2022). The most GNSS service disabling interference is done from high elevations above surface with the assistance of directional antennas and with high power. Act of jamming is illegal in the EU and many other regions (RED 2014/53/EU). There are multiple incentives to interfere with GNSS services, such as denying access to one's location information, to hinder critical infrastructures or to defence against outside military threats. The civilian users do not usually understand the illegality of jamming or severity of their actions because of false marketing of the devices or just by not understanding the principles of satellite positioning and its susceptibility to RFI. Most used jamming devices, aka jammers, are in-car jammers which are marketed for protecting personal

information. The problem is that this kind of jamming is not strictly local phenomenon since jammers interfere GNSS receivers beyond personal range. Jamming is an emerging threat to satellite positioning services and the consequences are diverse.

Interference has the most paralyzing effect on critical applications of GNSS, such as electricity transmission networks timing data or air traffic. Positioning accuracy that can be achieved with different services, such as the High Accuracy Service (HAS), is impressively precise which can be affected significantly by jamming (Kuusniemi et al., 2012). Anti-interference capabilities of the GNSS receiver determine how effective jamming can be. Jammer fingerprinting and other interference detection techniques can be used to combat against interference (Savolainen et al., 2024; Axell et al., 2015; Morrison et al., 2022).

In addition to being an emerging threat for everyday life, jamming is also a threat in conflicts (Kosola & Jokinen, 2004; Westbrook, 2019; Morrison et al., 2021). RFI can be utilized in electronic warfare (EW) as attacking or protecting purposes, such as defence for location-based measures. Electronic warfare is a part of modern military operations and nations invest significantly in EW equipment and soldier education.

This GNSS jamming signal simulation study emphasizes how spatially effective interference can be created and how jamming signal propagates in different kind of topographies and built-up areas in Finland. The purpose of this research is to exemplify how easily interference can be created and how efficient interference is in different Finnish landscapes with different jamming powers.

Research questions:

How does the topography and buildings affect the propagation of a jamming signal?

Can MATLAB's RF tools be used to simulate jamming signals on different topographies?

1.1 Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)

GNSS, Global Navigation Satellite System, is a complex system that consists of combination of following: electromagnetic spectrum (specifically radio signals), satellites, sensors, receivers, control systems and users. These components create a constellation that can be divided into three segments: the space, ground and user segment (Groves, 2013). EUSPA (European Union Agency for the Space Programme) defines GNSS as “a constellation of satellites providing signals from space that transmit positioning and timing data to GNSS receivers” (EUSPA, 2023a).

At the moment there are four global satellite navigation systems: European Galileo maintained by the European Space Agency (ESA), the U. S. Global Positioning System (GPS) from the United States Department of Defence, the GLObal Navigation Satellite System (GLONASS, Global'naya Navigatsionnaya Sputnikovaya Sistema in Russian) from the Russian Aerospace Defence Forces and the Chinese BeiDou Navigation Satellite System (BDS or sometimes BeiDou) administrated by CNSA (the China National Space Administration). These four GNSS's differ in terms of number of satellites, orbital planes, orbital height and temporal coverage as tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. The characteristics of different GNSS's

GNSS	Start of operations	Satellites	Orbital planes	Orbital height (km)	Orbit type	Orbital period (hours)	Notes
Galileo	2016	30	3	23 222	MEO	14	Full Operational Capacity hasn't been reached yet
GPS	1978	24	6	~ 20 200	MEO (Medium Earth Orbit)	12	Available to public in 1995
GLONASS	1982	24	3	~ 19 100	MEO	11	
BDS	2012	30	3	35 786	MEO& GEO (Geostationary Orbit)	12	

The performance of GNSS can be assessed by four criteria: accuracy, integrity, continuity and availability (EUSPA, 2023a). The first GNSS was GPS which was developed in the late 1970s but was opened for civilian use in 1995 (Söderholm et al., 2016). The newest and increasingly important

system is the European Galileo, which launched the first satellites in 2011 and started the initial service stage in the 2016 (EC, 2024a).

There are also local satellite navigation systems to be used in collaboration with global systems to enable more accurate positioning services for specific areas. For example, Quasi-Zenith Satellite System (QZSS) is implemented by Japan to co-operate with GPS to produce more precise local positioning data locally (Fairheller & Terrill, 2017). Another local satellite navigation system is, also Asian system, Indian NAVIC (Navigation Indian Constellation; formerly IRNSS, the Indian Regional Navigational Satellite System), which is compatible with multiple, but not specified global GNSS's (ISRO 2023). There are also regional satellite-based augmentation systems (SBAS), such as EGNOS (the European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service), which improves the performance of GNSS's within Europe (EUSPA, 2023b).

Noteworthy is that only European Galileo is a civilian-origin and civilian-governed navigation system, while the other three global systems are of military-origin and governed by military. This means that in military-governed systems civilian services could be denied or degraded anytime if wanted. The Galileo programme is funded by the European Union (EU) and the usage of funds are determined by the mutual agreement of the EU countries. The decision-making process is divided between ESA and the European Commission (EC). The EC is in charge of high-level mission requirements and political dimension of the system, while the responsibility of ESA is to lead space segment and ground elements, such as developing new technologies (ESA, 2023). The FOC (Full Operational Capacity) phase is managed and funded by the EC.

Satellite positioning is based on observing the distance between the user and satellites by acquiring and tracking satellite signals. Satellite signals are received by radio device of the receiver, which consists of antenna and receiving unit (Poutanen, 2016). Receiver's characteristics have a key role in positioning accuracy and the usage of different GNSS's. GNSS receivers are devices that are designed to receive satellite signals in one or multiple frequencies from one or multiple satellite systems. Receivers that acquire signals at only one frequency band are usually suitable for navigation, but multifrequency equipment that receives satellite signals from multiple GNSS's can provide more accurate and reliable positioning data when receiving signal from multiple systems simultaneously.

Satellite signals (i. e. radio signals) are transmitted from the satellites in different frequencies which are defined by satellite bands. The number of carrier frequencies and bands vary depending on the used GNSS system. Normally there are three bands but the number of different signals within the

band range between two and three. Every satellite signal has their own carrier frequency, which ranges between 1164 MHz–1610 MHz broadcasting satellite signal (Subirana et al., 2011).

The distance between satellite and receiver can be calculated either with a method that calculates the carrier phase or with an approach that calculates code phase for the acquired signal (Poutanen, 2016). Receiver creates replica of the satellite signal, and according to chosen method, it compares it to code or carrier phase and then calculates the delay of the signal from the comparison. The carrier phase method counts the numbers of wavelengths between the receiver and satellite and provides the positioning data relative to some previously known position, such as base station. In code phase method, the distance between receiver and satellite can be calculated at simplest by using the code of the satellite signal and multiplying the delay of satellite signal and speed of light, which results to absolute positioning data. In order to calculate positioning information, the receiver must have line-of-sight (LOS, an imaginary line between observer and the target) for at least four satellites. Here three satellites provide information of the position (x, y, z), while the fourth one gives timing information of the receiver's clock, which enables the calculation of the exact distance of the time difference between satellite and receiver. If this requirement for four satellites is compromised, accurate positioning data cannot be acquired. Receivers for navigation purposes, such as smartphones and car navigators, use code method for acquiring the distance measurements.

Due to the high orbital position of the satellite, approximately 20 000 kilometers, the signal travelling through the atmosphere to the Earth is weak, which makes them vulnerable for radio and other interference. Unintentional interference takes place due to the troposphere and space weather or broken devices such as broken radios transmitting signals at the GNSS frequency bands. Intentional interference is usually done with specific, malice goal in mind with specific devices, such as jammers. Different incentives, such as hiding own position for illegal activities, conduct interference tempting even for civilians let alone interference for military targets. Jamming can also be done intentionally, but unaware of its consequences for civilians. In-car jammers, that are used to hide own location, are the typical reason for increased jamming incidents.

Main services provided by GNSS are timing and positioning information, which are widely used in our society since many applications rely on this information. The accurate timing and location information from satellites are used, for example, for critical infrastructures such as bank transactions and electricity transmission networks utilizing the precise timing information. Navigation services, whether maritime or aviation, are also highly dependent on positioning data. There are also multiple

other applications that use positioning data, such as scientific research, logistics and road tolls. Position and location data is also often used in social media services and their geotags.

Safety-critical applications of GNSS, such as emergency services, are highly dependent on positioning data. The usage of GNSS services is similar between civilian use and use by authorities. However, the authorities can additionally access encrypted signals and services such as Search and Rescue (SAR) which is integrated to international multi-constellation COSPAS-SARSAT alert detection and information distribution satellite system (GSC 2020). For example, ambulances use navigation systems and SAR service for finding the scene of an accident. Interference for these services can be lethal. In 2022, Finnish Emergency Response Centre Agency (Hätäkeskuslaitos in Finnish) reported interference in national border areas of Eastern Finland (Hätäkeskuslaitos, 2022). The interference against satellite positioning in Eastern Finland had only small-scale effect on positioning of emergency calls.

1.2 Radio signals

Electromagnetic waves are energy that propagate from the Sun through space by Maxwell's equations (Thomas et al., 1973). Radio waves are the longest electromagnetic waves that radiate through space. Radio signals are located on exact frequencies of a radio wave which are used to carry information. In wireless communication systems signals are sent through air in a form of electromagnetic waves, hence satellite signals are radio signals carrying navigation and timing data. Radio signals can be received by the receivers using their antennas designed for reception or transmission of electromagnetic signals. Antennas are designed with desirable reception and radiation characteristics, such as directivity and antenna geometrics (Das, 2005). The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) under United Nations (UN), coordinates the shared global use of the radio spectrum (Subirana et al., 2011).

According to Rappaport (1999) modeling of radio channels (i. e. frequencies) is usually based on measurements that are made for specific spectrum allocation. For example, satellite signals operate on ultra-high frequencies (UHF), such as 0.3–30 GHz which are applied e. g. in the field of telecommunications technology and wireless communication engineering (Siwiak, 2007). Multidisciplinary research, such as mathematical and engineering research, have produced wireless communication systems by simulating the electromagnetic waves.

Radio signals attenuate when they propagate through the air. The received power in the receiver is a function of distance, frequency and the characteristics of the medium through which they travel. The free space loss formula calculates signal's attenuation in terms of distance and frequency. Free-space loss formula that ITU (International Telecommunication Union) recommends to use for free-space attenuation is:

$$L_{bf}(dB) = 32.4 + 20 \log f + 20 \log d \quad (\text{Formula 1})$$

where L_{bf} is free-space basic transmission loss (in dB), d is path length (in km) and f is frequency (in MHz) (ITU, 2019). With this formula free-space path loss of Galileo's E1 signal/ GPS's L1 signal (1575,42 MHz) for one kilometer would be 96.35 dB, for five kilometers 110.33 dB and for 10 kilometers 116.35 dB.

The transmission path of signal between receiver and transmitter varies from simple line-of-sight path to severely multipathed (i. e. diffracted) and disrupted paths (Rappaport, 1999). Satellite signals, which are radio signals, propagate due to the free space loss propagation formula (Formula 1) but they are impacted by terrestrial obstacles. The terrestrial obstacles remodel path of the signal into multipath propagation, which refers to the phenomenon where signal is received from multiple paths due to obstacles. These terrestrial obstacles, such as trees, buildings or other physical blocks, reflect satellite signals. Especially urban environments are challenging for GNSS, and thus they are characterized as "highly attenuated signal environments" (Lachapelle et al., 2004). In urban areas, the positioning accuracy is typically low by the penetrated and multipathed signals. Accuracy may be deteriorated even more by interference which may lead to unavailable GNSS services. It can also be difficult or at least more time-consuming to obtain position data, because the requirement for a connection to four satellites might not be fulfilled. When signals are multipathed due to dense material, such as topographic heights like mountain, they diffract. Higher frequencies are less impacted by diffraction loss (Salous, 2013).

Radio signals can also be affected by penetration loss caused by obstruction when signal travels through different materials. The fading of signal depends on the material it penetrates. For example, L1 signal of GPS fades more when entering a concrete and steel building than a residential garage (Lachapelle et al., 2004). Tanghe et al. (2008) presented that LOS path is not dominant and that building and ground reflections have effect on received power. The LOS path was 10 decibels lower compared to the power of reflected paths. Lachapelle et al. (2004) also demonstrated that reflected echo-signals of multipath environments lead to significant measurement errors in positioning accuracy.

This research concentrates on jamming devices that are usually used inside car. Vogel et al. (1996) observe that no direct LOS propagation path exists inside car and power of signal is strongly multipathed from scattering from edges of vehicle. In other words the received power of jamming signals are stronger due to multipath scattering and therefore jamming in areas with obstructions could be more effective. In general satellite signals propagate well in free space but are strongly attenuated in urban environments.

The power of satellite signals can also be defined as decibel-milliwatts (dBm). Usually dBm's are used to indicate the power of received signals. Decibel-milliwatt defines power level expressed in decibels with reference to one milliwatt and its absolute power. Formula for calculating dBm is:

$$P_{dBm} = 10 \log \frac{P_1}{1 \text{ mW}} \quad (\text{Formula 2})$$

in which P_1 power is normalized to one milliwatt (Sobot 2012). With this formula one watt would be 30 decibel-milliwatts and ten watts would be 40 decibel-milliwatts.

Satellite radio signals are received in receiver devices that create a copy of the GNSS signal. Different satellite systems and frequencies need their own signal channels which means hundreds of frequency bands (Poutanen, 2016). The most valuable factor in the receiving equipment is the antenna which receives the radio signals from different directions.

1.3 Positioning accuracy

Positioning accuracy depends on combination of receiver characteristics, possible additional positioning data, satellite visibility, satellite geometry, observed obstacles and used GNSS's. All GNSS systems operate with same principles, but they have differences in capacity, such as satellite visibility or additional positioning services. One of the important single element of positioning accuracy is the capabilities of used receiver. The calculation method of receiver affects positioning accuracy. Carrier phase measurements offer centimeter-scale, relative positioning data, but code phase measurements offer meter-scale, absolute positioning data (Poutanen, 2016). The relative positioning means determining the position with other known positions i. e. the observed position is relative to known positions, such as base station data. At least two receivers are needed in relative positioning to determine positions accurately. Absolute positioning data provided by code phase measurements is created with one receiver without additional corrections. Therefore consumer-grade GNSS receivers, that use code phase measurements, provide less accurate positioning data. Code

phase measurements are simpler to calculate. Geodetic measurements, that need highly accurate positioning data, are done with receivers using carrier phase measurements.

One method to improve relative positioning data is to use differential GNSS (DGNSS) by utilizing base station data. Base stations are permanent stations with positioning equipment. They make it possible to inspect temporal sources of errors as well as the quality of GNSS signals by comparing the receiver's positioning data to base stations actual position (Kaasalainen et al., 2021:7). The receiver corrects the position data of observed satellites before calculating its own location (Poutanen, 2016). With base station data the accuracy of positioning can be improved to centimeter level instead of meters, which is the default range for positioning with a single receiver. The FinnRef network of base stations in Finland has almost 50 stations all over Finland and with their positioning information the positioning accuracy can be approximately 50 centimetres. FinnRef is part of the International GNSS Service (IGS) providing high-quality and open access GNSS data (Katsigianni et al., 2019b). Real-time DGNSS corrections are shared from these base stations with NLS's FINPOS service via internet free of charge.

In order to improve absolute positioning data to centimeter-scale Precise Point Positioning (PPP) can be used. PPP technique aims to mitigate positioning error by utilizing exact information about satellite's orbit, clock correction data and Earth orientation parameters (Poutanen, 2016). The correction information is broadcasted via internet connection and provided by global network of reference stations that collect data about satellite signals. Errors in orbit information affect the absolute positioning accuracy directly, while in relative positioning that kind of error is insignificant. Relative positioning compares the dissimilarities between receiver's information and calculates a difference of the pseudodistances between observed satellites. Absolute positioning does not have excess information to compare the received data. In the use of PPP, the data is in the same coordinate system used by the satellite itself and therefore the coordinate conversion must be done by the user.

The performance of different GNSS systems vary by used indicators. In Xu et al. (2022), GPS and Galileo had better time transfer performance than BDS and GLONASS. In some studies that tested precise positioning performance GPS has been slightly more accurate (2–4 mm) compared to Galileo, but Galileo has been more accurate in horizontal accuracy (Katsigianni et al., 2019a; Hadas et al., 2019). Noteworthy is that Galileo system is younger than GPS, and in Hadas et al. performance testing in 2019 Galileo was nearly as good as GPS. Nowadays Galileo is considered to be more accurate than GPS, especially compared to the situation in 2019 when Galileo had not reached the needed size of satellite segment, had not yet introduced the HAS service and FOC has not yet been reached. The global PDOP (Position Dilution of Precision) value for 5° elevation mask (elevation angle of

satellites) was on average from 2.1 to 3 when for GPS it was on average 2.8. The PDOP value indicates the quality of satellite geometry, i. e. the 3D distribution of satellites in space (Dominy & Duncan, 2001; Poutanen, 2016). Values lower than 5 indicate better satellite geometry leading to better positioning accuracy. Compared to research by Pan et al. (2019) done in 2016, Galileo's PDOP value had improved twice as good for 10° elevation mask in performance test carried out by Hadas et al. (2019). In 2016, PDOP range was 6.0–8.2, while in 2019, the average value was 3.9. GPS and Galileo (without additional services) are considered to be the most accurate GNSS's in Europe and the US, but GLONASS and BDS are better in their primary areas of usage, in Russia and China. In Northern Finland the best coverage of satellites is by Russian GLONASS due to the weak satellite geometry of GPS and Galileo.

Infrequently only one GNSS is used for positioning. Normally there are multiple GNSS signals in use and positioning data is received from multiple GNSS's simultaneously, but usage can be limited to one GNSS by receiver. In Ashour et al. (2022), it was found out that the use of multiple GNSS systems as a combination improved positional accuracy compared to the use of individual system only. Cai et al. (2015) also determined that quad-constellation (i. e. global GNSS's) significantly improves the accuracy of precise point positioning (PPP) compared to the use of singular or dual-constellation. Besides positioning needs, precise point positioning is used also for geodetic applications.

The importance of multi-GNSS data was highlighted in Defraigne & Baire (2011) study in which GLONASS data combined to GPS timing data improved PPP, and in Katsigianni et al. (2019a) in which Galileo data combined to GPS data provided better positioning accuracy. The results improved by 28%–33% compared to case of using GPS only. In addition, in Gao et al. (2015), combination of GPS, BDS and GLONASS data with RTK (real time kinetic) positioning improved positioning accuracy approximately five centimeters. Testing different GNSS's and their combinations in Kirkkonummi, Finland, showed that the best horizontal 50% error value of 1.38 meters was from combination of GPS, Galileo and BDS (Söderholm et al., 2016). This 50% error means that 50% of the time the positioning error will be equal or below the value. The best single constellation was GPS with 50% error resulting to 2.98 in meters. The best vertical 50% error value, 2.49 m, was from Galileo. The constellation combinations were worse compared to Galileo only, although Galileo programme was just recently started. GLONASS was not tested by Söderholm et al. (2016).

When seeking for best navigation performance, the visibility of satellites is crucial as in some geographical locations GPS satellites are more visible than other GNSS systems and vice versa. The factors affecting satellite visibility are global constellation coverage and coverage time in different

geographical areas in addition to topography around the receiver's location. Söderholm et al. (2016) studied during a 24-hour-period the global visibility of combination of GPS, Galileo and BDS and found out that there were at least more than eight satellites globally and at best 22 satellites available. Pan et al. (2017), resulted to visibility ranging globally between 20 and 35 satellites when using GPS, Galileo, BDS and GLONASS for two-month test period. The best visibility of satellites can be reached in open, and flat areas without buildings.

Challenging environments for the visibility are urban areas with narrow streets and tall buildings. In Hadas et al. (2019), there were usually two more satellites visible for GPS compared to Galileo during a test week that calculated GPS and Galileo satellite positions every five minutes above 10° elevation angle over the horizon. The result is evidently affected by the incompleteness of Galileo system at the time when research was carried out. The satellite visibility of Galileo is most likely significantly better nowadays. Falco et al. (2017) proved in urban environment that usage of multiple constellations improved positioning accuracy when the visibility of the satellites that belong to only one constellation were reduced. Katsigianni et al. (2019a) also note that multi-GNSS solutions have higher satellite geometry diversity which improves positioning accuracy, but Falco et al. (2017) argue that alongside satellite geometry the performance of receivers also affects the visibility of the satellites. Other solution for improving the high-precision positioning is to enhance integer ambiguity of carrier phase i. e. to solve the number of measured cycles (Katsigianni et al., 2019b).

To improve PNT (Position, Navigation and Timing) reliability and accuracy, one solution is GNSS augmentation service called SBAS (Satellite-Based Augmentation System) which supports regional positioning, even for continental scale. Galileo's positioning service, the High Accuracy Service (HAS) is at the moment the world's most accurate positioning service with horizontal positioning accuracy of 20 cm and vertical accuracy of 40 cm (GSC 2023).

1.4 Interference

The susceptibility to RFI (radio frequency interference) is a serious threat to GNSS's. Satellite navigation services can easily be interfered with intent or unintentionally due to the weak power of satellite signals. Interference means disturbance for communication connections. The definition of interference can be characterized in various ways. According to Dovic (2015) any electromagnetic source that interacts with signals is interfering, but Ward et al. (2017) state that interference is produced by radio frequency signals received from undesired sources. In general interference can be defined as action which affects the normal usage of satellite navigation systems and their services. Interference can be divided into two groups: intentional and unintentional interference. Intentional interference is done with some end-goal in mind, such as disrupting GNSS positioning services, when unintentional interference can be for example out-of-band emissions from other radio frequency transmitters that overpower expected signals or multipath signals created by obstacles.

RFI is disturbance to systems that use radio signals, such as satellite navigation systems. Interference is fairly easy to accomplish since the power of received satellite signals is low. Heng et al. (2013) underline this by stating that "security is not a built-in-feature of GNSS open service". The vulnerability of GNSS's creates incentives to interfere for attackers who want to impair or fool GNSS systems (Margaria & Pini, 2015)

Satellite signals travel through space from the distance of approximately 20 000 kilometers. The exact distance depends on navigation system's own orbit altitude which is different for each GNSS system. On average the power level of satellite signal is -130 dBm (Elango et al., 2022a; Spirent 2018). In studies on GPS and Galileo signals chosen sensitivities have been between -140 and -160 dBm (Leclère et al., 2018). In Galileo's interface control document received minimum power level of E1 signal is approximately -127.25 dBm (converted from dBW; -157.25 dBW) which will be the sensitivity value for simulations applied in the simulations in this research (OS SIS ICD, 2023). Due to these low power levels of received signal it is possible to overpower satellite signals with even low-power interference devices, such as jammers.

The effect of interference varies from the characteristics of interference's source. Factors that define interference effectivity are power, orientation and vertical location of interference device. The power of interference is logically the most effective factor. Higher power means more effective interference. The power unit of interference devices that use radio signals is watt (W). Other highly effective factor is the orientation. Interference can be directed by sending signals to wanted direction with directional

antennas. Some jammers have antennas, which remodel the signal pattern of jamming. Antennas can be directed or they can have special characteristics, such as specific radiation patterns. Kuusniemi et al. (2012) note that “in all receivers intentional jamming affects the signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) of the received signals”. The receiver cannot create ranging measurements when the SNR decreases and signals get weaker. The objective of jamming is to make the GNSS receiver to either lose signal and its position data or to prevent signal reacquiring.

The vertical location, such as height of the antenna, create a difference for the spatial effectiveness of interference, since the signal can be propagated in specific height. The most effective interference is caused from high elevation so that interference signal can propagate without obstacles to the environment. Air-borne interference can be done for example from an airplane, a drone or a balloon. In that case the interference signal propagates freely to the environment without obstacles, compared to the scenario where interference is done from the ground where signal will run into obstacles.

Interference is more effective and severe if there is only one navigation satellite system or frequency in use, for example if a navigator or mobile phone uses only one system for receiving the PNT services. In this kind of scenario interference blocks or interrupts user to receive data, while in multi-GNSS scenario the signals in non-interfered frequency bands would come through. Interference is thus frequency-specific. Nowadays most smartphones support multiple GNSS's. For example, iPhone model 12 and newer models support all global GNSS's, as well as for example smartphones with Android-operating system such as Android 8.0 and newer models with newer Android operating systems (Dabove et al., 2020). iPhone model 12 is a single frequency model and therefore does not provide protection over general L1 jammers, but model 15 is a dual-frequency model and therefore more protected. Usually the limitations of smartphones regarding (highly) precise positioning are due to the used antennas which for example have susceptibility to multipath (Paziewski, 2020).

1.4.1 Unintentional interference

Interference is divided into two categories: intentional and unintentional. Unintentional interference is interference that is not originated from intentional or malicious action. Elango et al. (2022a) classify unintentional interference into three classes, ionospheric effects, multipath and signal blockage, while Ward et al. (2017) divides unintentional interference into two classes: ionospheric scintillation and multipath. Bhuyian et al. (2014) point out that it's important to identify the source of interference correctly so mischievous action can be identified from unintentional interference such as multipath.

The ionospheric disturbance, such as high solar activity, cause signals to be less accurate because of increased background noise (de Paula et al., 2022). High solar activity causes disturbance to GNSSs especially in high latitudes. The electron concentration of ionosphere delays signals propagation.

Unintentional RFI can also be caused by different factors inside the frequency band, by faulty equipment or multipath propagation. It is possible to have interference in or near the frequency band of satellite signals. Out-of-band interference stems from interfering signals whose carrier frequency is located near or targeted GNSS frequency band, such as analog TV channels, cell phones or laptops (Dovis et al., 2015). It is also possible to have interfering signals with carrier frequency within the GNSS band. For example, tactical air navigation systems, that have high-power pulsed signals, use Galileo's E5a and E5b (1164–1214 MHz) signal frequencies and create a threat to GNSS receivers. Also, intersystem interference inside a receiver is possible when several GNSS's share the same carrier frequency. Faulty equipment, such as broken radio devices, might broadcast signals in wrong frequencies.

Multipath signals means that signals are reflected or redirected by some obstacle, such as topography, trees and buildings on their way to the receiver. Therefore, certain areas, such as densely built urban areas or forests, are more prone to multipath. The reflection or redirection of signal means that the direct LOS from the satellite to the receiver is compromised and the satellite signal is not reliable. Multipath can be seen as self-interference, since interfering signals are replicas, reflections, of original satellite signal (Dovis, 2015).

1.4.2 Intentional interference

Yang et al. (2022) rank interference according to their harmfulness in ascending order as follows: multipath, jamming and spoofing. Spoofing and jamming are both intentional interference and they both affect positioning by giving user incorrect information about their position. Jamming degrades the positional accuracy or blocks the calculation of navigation solution when spoofing makes user believe their position is totally different that it is. Spoofing is done by broadcasting false GNSS signal to the user, for example in maritime navigation it might seem that a vessel is on the right course but actually the course is totally different. For example, Morrison et al. (2023), note that spoofing lead to ridiculous “superhuman feats” that were recorded by fitness tracking app. Low end receivers, such as mobile phones, cannot detect spoofed satellite signal and some high-end systems have difficulties as well. By using joint interference, jamming and spoofing at the same time, it is possible to achieve

wanted level of spoofing interference with low power when the target is jammed at the same time (Miljanovic et al., 2022).

Both kinds of interference affect the safety of GNSS services by affecting the quality of received PNT information. Even though spoofing is remarkable threat for GNSS services it can only be conducted by professionals and therefore it poses a threat to selected and specified targets when jamming affects comprehensively. The U. S. Department of Homeland Security has defined Global Positioning System as critical infrastructure whose greatest danger is jamming (RNT Foundation, 2016).

1.4.3 Jamming

Jamming is intentional interference that is done with jamming device (aka jammer) by broadcasting carrier signal in specific satellite signal frequency. Collection of online-sold low-power jammers are portrayed in Figure 1. Jammer can be defined as “any apparatus, designed, used, intended or adapted for the purposes of causing deliberate interference to radiocommunications” (ECC Recommendation (04)01). Carrier signal sent from jammer doesn’t contain any information that satellite navigation signal would, such as code modulation or orbit and satellite clock data. Jamming can therefore be characterized as intentional transmission of radio frequency energy to block a PNT service by masking satellite signals with noise or as a denial-of-service attack with noise-like signal (Dovis, 2015; Miljanovic et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Online-sold low-power jammers. On the left typical in-car jammer, in the middle a jammer disguised as an USB flash drive and on the right portable jammer.

The goal of jamming is to prevent tracking or to disorientate positioning information and hinder the usage of navigation information. Jamming affects positional accuracy by completely preventing acquisition of the positioning data or decreasing the spatial accuracy of positioning data. Decreased accuracy of position or entirely unavailable positioning information affects users of satellite navigation in multiple ways. The users of satellite navigation systems are vast varying from single users to critical infrastructures. For example, positioning and accurate timing data is needed in car navigators, money transactions and transmission of electricity.

The results of jamming are vast. Unavailable or incorrect positioning data can lead to errors in positioning services used by authorities, such as emergency authorities and police. Without accurate positioning data first-aid help will delay if the main source of positioning data is navigation services provided by GNSS. Paralyzing effects of jamming affect air traffic and infrastructures that use precise timing data. Unavailable positioning and timing data for critical infrastructures can have entirely paralyzing effect on societies.

Jamming has been an increasing threat for GNSS from the early two-thousands when the intentional degradation of GPS signals was discontinued (Swider et al., 2000). Well-known incidents are for example the Iraq War missile diversion, Newark airport incident and jamming of NATO Trident

Juncture 2018. In the Iraq War GPS signal was jammed by Iraqi forces from on top of landmarks to prevent areas from being hit by missiles (Greenemeier, 2016). The accidental jamming of Newark airport in 2010 caused severe interference on air traffic control by affecting the local-area augmentation system of GPS (Dovis, 2015). The origin of jamming was truck drivers near the area who used jammers. Due to this one driver was fined 32 000 USD for interference.

One of the widely internationally noted jamming incidents was the jamming of NATO military exercise Trident Juncture in 2018 which resulted in large disturbance in aviation navigation. Due to the interference Finnish air navigation authorities issued a NOTAM (Notice to Airmen) about extensive losses of GNSS signal and navigation services in Lapland (Leisti, 2018). This NOTAM was the first ever due to interference in Finnish areas. Jamming has been a nuisance also in the Ukraine war. Russia has extensive set of interference equipment and the interference has also been reaching different areas of Finland and the Baltic Sea (Halminen, 2024; Rummukainen, 2023). Nowadays jamming is a well-known and common threat for the military operations (Kosola & Jokinen, 2004; Westbrook, 2019; Morrison et al., 2021). There are also more incentives for civilian jamming in terms of privacy protection as the Newark incident demonstrated (Dovis, 2015).

The Finnish Transport and Communications Agency (Traficom) monitors jamming events in Finland. There are instruments observing jamming in Finnish cities and other populated areas. The yearly amount of observed jammers is couple of hundred devices, but the number of observed jammers has an increasing trend (Traficom, 2023b). Observed jammer type is usually an in-car jammer. The number of observations however can be influenced by a jammer that is used continuously in the same area multiple times.

Jamming testing is usually carried out in carefully controlled laboratory environments that prevent the GNSS jamming signal to escape the test area, such as anechoic chambers. Kuusniemi et al. (2012) conducted a jamming signal testing for different consumer-grade receivers with affordable (20–130 USD) jammers inside a laboratory. With maximum tested power of 25 dB the result of jamming was position's shift with maximum horizontal error varying between 16.4 and 129.3 meters. Jamming testing and detection is limited by the illegality of jamming but some real environment studies have been made. When GNSS jamming was tested in real environment by Morong et al. (2019), the experiment proved that low-power jamming signal propagates well in free space but in real outdoor environment the signal must be stronger to propagate through space with obstacles. This suggests that in order to create long range interference the power of jammer must be relatively high, more than approximately 1.5 watts that was used in the experiment.

Morrison et al. (2023) observed in their real environment jamming study that multi-band and multi-constellation receivers were able to generate positioning data under the presence of persistent jamming signal, but the timing synchronization, i. e. the timing data, was affected and accurate timing data was denied. In this study also low-cost receivers had resilience to interference and positioning data was generated even though the positioning accuracy had an error of hundreds of meters.

Jammers can be easily bought online despite the illegality of jamming. Usually, jammers are sold under the name of cell phone blocker or personal privacy device (PPD) (Jafarnia-Jahromi et al., 2013; Dovic et al. 2015: 43). These PPD's are normally designed to plug into a car cigarette lighter power outlet. Used jamming techniques are typically frequency altering methods such as transmitting chirp signals or using sweep tone method (Kuusniemi et al., 2012; Dovic et al., 2015). Kraus et al. (2011) note that in-car jammers are "particularly important" because their use allows vehicles to avoid being tracked which leads to misconceptions of the effect of jamming. Jammers can also be portable small devices disguised as harmless electronic devices such as cell phones (Axell et al., 2015).

Speculated powers of online-sold, freely available jammers range between hundreds of milliwatts to even 100 watts (Axell et al., 2019; Kuusniemi et al., 2012). A 100-watt jammer would be extremely harmful and would most likely be used in military scenarios rather than by privacy seeking citizens. There are some agent actors who claim to sell high-power jammers for exclusive consumer groups such as military forces and VIP security services. Example of these devices is a jammer for drones, such as German AARTOS -drone detection system devices which are told to have large jamming range due to their characteristics such as omnidirectional antenna, ability to interfere with multiple GNSS frequencies and power of tens of watts (AARTOS, 2024). There is a loophole for the market of these devices: sale of these devices is legal within European Union area even though using them is illegal. However, the technical capabilities of these commercial devices are questionable.

Generally, jammers and PPD's are marketed for protecting personal information such as location information, but the problem is that these jammers create interference everywhere around them. The marketed effective range can allegedly be only some meters and the interference can be informed to affect only the vicinity of car where the jammer typically is applied. Jamming is therefore not strictly local phenomenon since jammers interfere GNSS receivers beyond the personal range. Other problem that arises from PPD's is the regular usage and continuous effects on satellite positioning services, even though low power usually limits the effective range of jamming to fairly small areas.

The user group for jammers and PPD's are usually privacy seeking citizens who want to hide their location. In case of in-car jammers these can be truck drivers who want to hide their location

information from their employers when they have exceeded the legal driving time or a citizen who is for some reason paranoid about the tracking of their location information. There have been also some cases where jammers have been used in criminal activity such as car thefts and housebreakings (Alén-Savikko, 2019). Generally, the usage of these PPD's is not done on purpose in order to affect satellite positioning. The civilian users do not usually understand the severity of their actions because of false marketing of these devices or just by not understanding the principles of satellite positioning and its susceptibility to RFI. Therefore, ordinary people should be informed about the regulation and risks especially when jammers are sold online to anyone without precautions.

Consumer-grade jammers are sold typically as few hundreds of milliwatt power level devices. Nevertheless, the marketing is misleading in terms of power. Experts in the field of jamming have speculated that for example in alleged 500 mW jammers the power levels are closer to hundred milliwatts than 500 milliwatts and all in all the true power of these devices varies and can be as low as tens of milliwatts. This suggests that jammers sold online, from websites such as eBay or AliExpress, have unpredictable power levels. Also, the alleged frequencies of these jammers vary and the jamming can be directed to frequencies that were not mentioned in the advertisement. Example of advertisement of online-sold jammer is depicted in Figure 2.

A

Mini GPS Satellite Blocker

£38.00

FREE SHIPPING now! More than 2-8 meter coverage!

You have to try this MINI GPS Jammer to make sure the car security without tracking.

Pls plug the gps jammer into a standard 12V cigarette lighter to support power, then it will protect you automatically by blocking any GPS tracking.

If you are sales personnel and delivery drivers, this GPS tracking jammer is a very popular item for you to take lunch or make a personal stop outside of your territory or route "off the radar".

B

Working frequency: 1500-1600MHz
 Effective jamming coverage (radius): 2-8m
 To prevent GPS satellite positioning tracking
 Block GPS satellite signal to protect your privacy
 Charging Specifications: Cigarette Lighter (12v)
 Power adjustment range: 33dBm 6dBm/30KHz (min)
 Dimension: 75*20*20 mm
 Storage temperature: -50~+60°C
 Working temperature: -30~60°C
 Relative humidity: 5~95%
 Small size, high power, light weight, great coverage, easy to carry

We are a gps jammer factory! We will check the quality before shipped! Best service!

Figure 2. Advertising of an in-car jammer. A picture depicts the promises that are given to this “military-quality” device. B illustrates the parameters of the jammer. The power range of 33 dBm–6 dBm is equal to approximately 2 W–0.4 W. Picture: www.jammer4uk.com/product/mini-gps-satellite-blocker

At present these simple PPD jammers broadcast power at only one or two frequencies, such as L1 (1575.42 MHz) and L2 (1227.60 MHz), of GPS system despite the false marketing (Ávila Rodríguez, 2008; Mitch et al., 2011; Borio et al., 2013; Dovis et al., 2015). GNSS threat monitoring systems however monitor multiple frequency bands also for example Galileo bands E5 and E6 (Thombre et al., 2017). The range of jammers can vary from hundreds of meters to kilometers, depending on devices characteristics, such as antenna, power and the broadcasting frequency. Generally, Dovis et al. (2015) speculate that some researched jammers have had varying effective ranges from 300 meters to 8,5 kilometers and Morong et al. (2019) speculate that jammer with 2W power could block the acquisition of satellite signal up to 15 kilometers in free space. Effective range is mostly affected by the used power. Consumer grade jammers are usually low-power (Borio et al., 2013).

Some jammers have antennas, which remodels the signal pattern of jamming. Antennas can be directed or they can have special characteristics, such as specific radiation patterns. Kuusniemi et al. (2012) note that “in all receivers intentional jamming affects the signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) of the received signals”. The receiver cannot create ranging measurements when the SNR decreases and signals get weaker. The objective of jamming is to cause the receiver to either lose signal and its position data or to prevent signal reacquiring.

1.4.4 E1 and L1: the most interfered frequency bands

Since the structure of civilian GNSS signals is public, a jammer can generate a waveform with a structure similar to that of the authentic signals (Jafarnia-Jahromi et al., 2015). Therefore, jamming targets known frequencies from different GNSS's, such as Galileo's E1 and GPS's L1. The jamming signal doesn't contain any information that is needed for acquiring PNT data and can be considered as empty signal.

Most of the interference is done to Galileo's E1 and GPS's L1 band who share the same carrier frequency (1575.42 MHz) for E1 and L1 signals (Subirana et al., 2011; Bhuyian, 2014; Axell et al., 2015). In Morrison et al. (2022) observations in four monitoring stations in Norway and the Netherlands E1 and L1 bands experienced the most interference with expected RFI of averagely tens of seconds per day. The indifference between these two bands is that E1 band varies from 1559 MHz to 1591 MHz when L1 band varies from 1563 MHz to 1587 MHz (Àvila Rodriguez, 2011). E1 band is therefore wider and is sub-divided into two signals: E5a and E5b.

E1 and L1 signals are upper band (1559–1610 MHz) signals, which are considered to be less vulnerable to interference than the lower band (1151–1214 MHz) signals (Elango et al., 2022b). Both E1 and L1 signals carry Aviation Radio Navigation Service (ARNS) and Radio Navigation Satellite Service (RNSS) and are available worldwide. GNSS services utilize RNSS.

GPS's L1 and usually also Galileo's E1 signals reach a higher availability than other signals and are overall easier to acquire than e. g. GPS's L5 and Galileo's E5 (both in carrier frequency of 1191.795 MHz) , which both are also available for civilian use (Jafarnia-Jahromi et al., 2015; Leclère et al., 2018). Overall, it can be argued that GPS is the most used and usually also the most available system globally since it is the pioneer of GNSS and often used as a default navigation system in receivers.

1.5 Countermeasures against interference

1.5.1 Protection against interference

GNSS-based services will always be vulnerable to the presence of interfering signals (Dovis, 2015). However, GNSS receivers can have anti-interference capacity, such as simultaneous detection of multipath and jamming (Yang et al., 2022). According to Kuusniemi et al. (2012) there are also technical approaches for protecting satellite positioning, for example longer codes or dataless pilot signals. Also interfering multiple frequencies (i. e. signals) requires expensive and more complex jamming devices. Other anti-interference techniques are for example signal processing algorithms and sensors. Spoofing can also be characterized to be a demanding interference technique because it requires professional skills and devices.

In order to detect jamming, different techniques can be used. For example, an energy detector, such as radiometer, can be used to measure the energy of receive jamming signal (Axell et al., 2015). Antenna plays a role in the observed interference. Adaptive antennas, which radiation patterns are controlled, can ignore jamming signals that come from certain direction (Jones, 2011; Kraus et al., 2011). Elango et al. (2022b) claim that the most important way to combat jamming is to detect and characterize interfering signals. ARFIDAAS (the Advanced RFI Detection Analysis and Alerting System) is a monitoring system with additional hardware, to detect impacting RFI (Morrison et al., 2022). The monitoring system is built with captured real environment RFI and analyses of said RFI incidents. There is also ongoing research on fingerprinting jamming devices, which would make jammers more identifiable and jamming incidents more visible. In Savolainen et al. (2024), different jammers were tested and first steps to fingerprinting jamming devices were taken.

GNSS services are thoroughly monitored in Finland by the National Land Survey of Finland (NLS). For example, NLS's GNSS-Finland Service provides open data about the 'health' of satellites and signals. The service is based on FINPOS positioning services that utilize NLS's observation data from GNSS base stations (NLS, 2023a). Securing GNSS services is part of security of supply because GNSS services are considered as critical infrastructure.

To make openly used E1 and L1 signals less vulnerable, they could be protected by encrypting the signals. Encryption would make them less vulnerable for spoofing (unfortunately not entirely for jamming) but also more demanding to be utilized in civilian use. One solution for vulnerability issues could be usage of multi-constellation receivers. These types of receivers are able to provide PVT

solutions (Position, Velocity and Time) even in the presence of interfering signals due to low spectral overlap of shared frequency bands (i. e. shared by different GNSS's signals) (Jafarnia-Jahromi et al., (2015).

Galileo's E1 signals are made to bear jamming better than the older L1 with newer services such as the Public Regulated Service (PRS). The PRS is accessible to E1 signal. Galileo's E6 signal is also protected from intentional interference by encryption with the PRS which operates in a frequency band that is allocated for strictly authorized users, such as police and military. The PRS is considered to be the most sensitive but also the most secure service of Galileo and it's used in situations where "robustness and complete reliability must be ensured", such as emergency services or border surveillance (the European Parliament and Council decision 1104/2011/EU). Finland aims to start using the PRS in 2026 (Traficom, 2024). Interference on E6 signal has been researched for example by Morrison et al. (2021) and Arribas et al. (2019).

Norwegian authorities have been organizing a controlled, real environment jamming scenario testing event, Jammertest, for couple of years in remote areas of Northern Norway. This event aims to find solutions for developing safer solutions for PNT by carrying out equipment tests and system tests for global GNSS's (Jammertest, 2024). Dovis (2015) notes that interference "is one of the main limitations to the development of GNSS-based applications and services" and the unpredictability of interference makes it lethal. It is crucial for the scientific research and for the advancements in the industry of GNSS's to be able to test interference scenarios in real environments and various weather conditions to improve the resilience against RFI.

1.5.2 Legislation

In order to mitigate the threats of unintentional interference, citizens should be informed and educated about the legislation and usage of jamming devices (Ángel, 2008; Pattinson et al., 2017). Also, the illegality of jamming and RFI should be highlighted. When jammers are sold online, they do not usually have sufficient information about the illegality of jamming nor the effect of using a jamming device. Harmful interference can lead to fines and imprisonment in Finland and in other EU countries. Civilian use of jammers cannot be justified in any scenario but authorities, such as military, have exceptions to the use of RFI.

Radio frequencies are allocated and standardized by the ITU (the International Telecommunication Union) which is the United Nations specialized agency for information and communication

technologies (Subirana et al., 2011; ITU, 2024). European policy for radio frequencies is based on ITU's recommendations. The national enforcement of EU legislation is a responsibility of each state on their own. In Finland, Traficom monitors the usage of different radio frequencies. Traficom is allowed to inspect radio devices and areas where radio devices are used to ensure that correct frequencies are used. Act on Electronic Communications Services (917/2014) in Finnish law defines harmful interference as “interference which endangers the functioning of radio navigation or of other safety radio communications or which otherwise seriously degrades radio communications or radiodetermination operating in accordance with the applicable regulations or obstructs or repeatedly interrupts such operations”.

According to the Finnish Radio Act (Radio Act 1988/517, *radiolaki* in Finnish) it is forbidden to use radio jamming device, and it is criminalized, i. e. it is illegal to use one. According to the Radio Act chapter 1, section 12:

If a radio transmitter causes interference in radio communications or other radio equipment, the holder of the radio transmitter shall eliminate or restrict the interference. If interference in radio communications is caused by technical characteristics of a radio receiver, the elimination of the interference shall be the obligation of the holder of the receiver. The holder of radio equipment shall also undertake all other measures ordered by the Telecommunications Administration Centre in order to eliminate or restrict the interference or its effects.

However, possession of a jammer is not illegal, but according to the Radio Equipment Directive (RED) 2014/53/EU guidelines “it is not possible to construct jammers that fulfil the EMC (Electromagnetic Compatibility Directive, 2014/30/EU) and radio essential requirements”. Therefore, jamming devices should be withdrawn from the market (RED Guide, 2018).

In Finnish jammer scenarios these devices, typically low-power in-car jammers, are often found from their users' cars where they are used to hide location data (Traficom, 2023b). The amount of detected jammers has increased. In Finland an official, such as a police chief, can conduct a search for a domicile if there's a reason to suspect a crime and if alleged that it's possible to find an object that should be confiscated (Coercive Measures Act 806/2011, 8:2, *pakkokeinolaki* in Finnish). Police officer can conduct a search and confiscate an illegal good, such as jammer, if they can prove that illegal good was just used. Unfortunately, in-car jammers and other simple jammers can be easily switched off, which means that proving of usage might be difficult. Also, a search warrant can be

conducted for a car if it is justified for confiscating illegal goods (Act 806/2011, 7:1). In Finnish Coercive Measures Act (806/2011) domicile also includes cars if they are not inhabited.

If violating the section 12 of the Radio Act, sanctions may be a fine or gravely imprisonment. The punitive sanctions of illegal actions are stated in the section 20 of the Radio Act as it rules that the punishment of radio communications interference is regulated in the Finnish Criminal Code (19.12.1889/39, in Finnish *rikoslaki*) chapter 38 sections 5 to 7. The offence can be conventional or aggravated. Even the attempt is criminalized. According to the Criminal Code chapter 38 section 5:

A person who, by tampering with the operation of a device used in postal, telecommunications or radio traffic, by maliciously transmitting interfering messages over radio or telecommunications channels or in another equivalent manner, unlawfully interferes with or impedes postal, telecommunications or radio traffic shall be sentenced for interference with communications to a fine or to imprisonment for at most two years. An attempt is punishable.

As it seems, continuous intentional interference may lead to a fine or imprisonment for violation of the provisions on radio equipment. If one interferes with or endangers radio communications, and the circumstances are considered to be intentional, one can be sentenced for aggravated violation of the provisions on radio equipment to imprisonment of maximum of two years. Alén-Savikko (2019) notes that usage of jammers in any civilian scenario cannot be justified, but authorities may use jammers to prevent the passage of unmanned aerial vehicles or drones.

Jamming is also illegal in the area of the European Union and EEA (European Economic Area) States, which are Liechtenstein, Iceland and Norway. According to the Radio Equipment Directive (RED) 2014/53/EU second article paragraph 7 “‘harmful interference’ means interference which endangers the functioning of a radio navigation service or of other safety services or which otherwise seriously degrades, obstructs or repeatedly interrupts a radio communications service operating in accordance with the applicable international, Community or national regulations”. This directive defines the characteristics of radio equipment, for example harmful interference should be avoided with undamaged equipment which supports the efficient use of radio spectrum. Radio equipment should be also properly used, maintained and installed. Member states are responsible for monitoring the usage of radio equipment. Compared to this legislation in-car jammers, even small power devices, are definitely illegal under the Finnish law as well as in EU directive viewpoint. In-car jammers, aka personal privacy devices, endanger navigation services within its range which can lead to the loss of location data and its by-products.

Jamming is illegal also in other nations. In the United States the US federal law prohibits usage and sale of jamming equipment that interferes with satellite communications (The U. S. Criminal Code, Title 18 Section 1367(a); FCC, 2020; OLRC, 2024). In Canada the possession of jammer is illegal as well as interfering radio spectrum (Radiocommunication Act 1985).

1.6 Electronic warfare

GNSS interference is part of electromagnetic or electronic warfare (EMW or EW) which means “the use or manipulation of the electromagnetic spectrum in warfare from the air, land, sea and space” and it “includes any military action involving the use of electromagnetic and directed energy to control the electromagnetic spectrum or attack the enemy” (Pace, 2022). In other words, the main purpose of EW is to control the usage of electromagnetic spectrum. Kosola and Jokinen (2004) define EW through three main goals: intelligence gathering, paralysing and deceiving sensors and electronic systems and protecting troops. EW is considered to be part of information warfare since it can immobilize critical infrastructures and affect operational capability.

Sometimes a term navigation warfare (NAVWAR) is used when the subject is especially the interference of GNSS and no other frequencies, such as microwave frequencies for radar systems, are used. The birthplace of NAVWAR is considered to be the Iraq War (or the second Gulf War) in early two-thousands when the first GPS signal jamming attacks were conducted to confuse cruise missile guidance systems (Ko, 2010; Westbrook 2019). Due to this Morrison et al. (2021) note that military forces should be prepared to operate in environments that are unfriendly and contain intentional interference. Ward et al. (2017) underline this by stating that “intentional jamming and spoofing must be anticipated in the design of military receivers”. In a risk analysis for the U. S. and its dependency of GPS was highlighted that GPS is “a single point of failure for critical infrastructure” and military-style jamming along with terrorist jamming were seen as the most severe risks to GPS services (RNT Foundation, 2016).

Poisel (2014) divides electronic warfare to three subclasses: electronic support, electronic attack and electronic protection. Support is usually detecting or locating electromagnetic energy. Electronic attack means inserting false signals into receiving equipment and attack techniques usually exploit the flaws of sensors to e. g. degrade tracking capability (Genova, 2018). Electronic protection is actions that are taken to protect electromagnetic systems of being successfully attacked by operating

forces. The field of radar engineering develops techniques for electronic protection and one of the main interests of this field is target identification.

Jamming can be characterized as both electronic attack and electronic protection based on its purpose. Therefore, jamming can be done to either interfere and attack other GNSS users or to be protected from location-based measures, for example (cruise) missiles. Jamming attacks are conducted to e. g. misguide radar systems or drones.

It has been speculated that EW capabilities would be the defining factor of future wars and in Russian defence administration it is believed that the EW capabilities of different nations will determine the outcomes of future conflicts (Kjellén, 2018). Western nations invest in EW capabilities in form of materiel and education. For example, the Finnish Defence Forces trains soldiers for electronic warfare tasks and the Swedish Armed Forces have an entire electronic warfare battalion (Hägglom, 2024). There is also EW technology produced in Finland, e. g. state-owned company Patria produces technology solutions in the field of defence. Overall nations should be aware of their own capabilities against GNSS interference since it is emerging and already remarkable threat in conflict situations and during the peacetime.

Russia is regularly accused of jamming in different areas, such as in Finland, Norway and Syria during and off peacetime (Harrison et al., 2019). Different areas in Finland have been or are under continuous threat of GNSS jamming which originates to Russia (Leisti, 2018; Rummukainen, 2023; Bingen et al., 2023). Interference is covered on Finnish media especially when jamming affects air traffic.

The electronic warfare capabilities of Russia are impressive. The materiel catalogue of Russian armed forces includes automated jamming stations of different jamming equipment and complexes of EW systems and vehicles (Kjellén, 2018). The EW equipment utilizes multiple frequencies and powers and have directional antennas.

It can be said that the Russian invasion of Ukraine was one of the reasons why the Finnish defence budget increased by 20% when seeking to “respond to the changes in the operating environment” (Defmin, 2022). All in all, Finland has increased military spending by 89% in ten years due to equipment modernisation and changed geopolitical situations. However, the vast difference between 2024 and 2014 is partially explained by the downsizing, which took place in 2014 (Jonsson, 2024). The capabilities and readiness of the Finnish Defence Forces have improved over the last couple of years due to the new materiel.

2 DATA AND METHODS

The aim of the study is to create a numerical computation of electromagnetic waves, a specific satellite radio signal, over irregular terrain in different topographies and built-up areas in Finland. This study used free space loss (see 1.2. formula 1) propagation model on top of digital elevation data as a method for simulating jamming signals horizontal propagation over different topographies. The horizontal viewpoint was chosen to highlight the horizontal propagation along with free space propagation where signal propagates to every direction from transmitter.

Modelling of the signal propagation was chosen as a method, because research on signal propagation for jamming signals cannot be carried out applying field work methods. At the moment there are no GNSS jamming simulators that could simulate the propagation of jamming signals in different environments and jamming scenarios. There are GNSS jamming simulators, such as Orolia GSG-8 and Spirent GSS7765, that can be used to signal testing but the environmental effect, such as terrain topography and built-up area, on jamming signal cannot be shown. The spatial effects of jamming are an active research area at the Department of Computer Science in University of Helsinki (see e. g. Yan et al., 2023).

Due to the lack of appropriate method for jamming scenario simulations and existing simulators' limitations, licensed engineering software MATLAB (version R2021b) was used for modelling signal propagation. MATLAB can be used for numeric computing and programming and it is often used for data analysis and researching wireless communication, that includes satellite positioning technology as well.

2.1 Data

A digital elevation model (DEM) of 2 meters spatial resolution in x and y was used to create topographic characteristics for each research area. The DEMs, named Elevation model 2 m, were provided by the National Land Survey of Finland (NLS) in raster format and were retrieved from NLS's spatial data download service Karttapaikka. The chosen DEMs were provided in 6 km times 6 km square format. The elevation data is licensed by Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0 (NLS, 2023b). All elevation datasets were retrieved from NLS in November 2023. DEM takes topography into account and ignores terrains other aspects such as forest canopy or buildings.

The best quality DEM was applied for every research area, which has the average height accuracy of 30 centimetres of the elevation accuracy class 1. The elevation data of two-meter spatial resolution is the most accurate open access and free data available for Finnish areas. The elevation models are derived from laser scanning data with a minimum point density of 0,5 points per square meter. The product IDs and dates of laser scanning are presented in the Table 5(appendix 3). The DEMs are in ETRS89/ TM35FIN (EPSG:3067) reference system and the height values are in accordance with the N2000 system. Units of measurement are in meters.

The use of MATLAB for simulation causes some restrictions, such as limitation in the geographical area of the simulation. MATLAB is able to simulate the jamming scenario coherently for the size of available DEMs which are 6 times by 6 km. Larger areas can be chosen and downloaded from Karttapaikka, and simulations were tested on bigger DEMs, but for unresolved reasons they were not coherently simulated further than 6 kilometres horizontally. Figure 3 exemplifies the uncertainties of larger area simulations. To ensure the consistency of terrain data available DEM products were used.

MATLAB can simulate jamming over these NLS's data limitations by using default DEM data for unprovided areas, but the uncertainties still exist. The combination of NLS data and default data has the exact same difficulties causing empty areas and height differences inside the data which cannot be explained by topography. The default data provided by MATLAB is also not correct in terms of elevation. The difference between national data and default data is approximately two meters too high or too low in different areas. Therefore, the actual size of jamming is larger than presented in resulting figures, and speculated whole area of interference is presented in the appendices for every research area.

Figure 3. The limitations of a larger DEM visualization. MATLAB cannot visualize entire area of jamming scenario, but instead creates empty areas and height differences in data.

In urban research area, Punavuori in Helsinki, a combination of NLS's DEM and OpenStreetMap (OSM) building data was used to create and simulate the elevation differences and buildings of the area. OpenStreetMap is an open access and free map database created by GIS (Geographic Information System) community. Used data is licensed with The Open Database License (ODbL) v1.0. (OSM, 2024). The building data provided by OSM is similar to the buildings in satellite image of the area and therefore OSM data can be trusted for this purpose of use. Even if the building data was incorrect e. g. about the height information, it does not count on this study where horizontal signal propagation is considered in the height of 1.5 meters. OSM uses also NLS's Topographic Database datasets, but the exact origin of height data of the buildings is not available, so buildings can be either created by OSM (community) developers or they can be extracted from open dataset of NLS.

2.2 Research areas

The research areas were chosen to represent different areas in their topographic and man-made obstacles in Finland. The areas are in different parts of Finland, in Lapland, Uusimaa, Ostrobothnia and Kymenlaakso, more specifically in the municipality of Kolari and in the cities of Helsinki, Seinäjoki and Kotka (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Map of research areas.

The research areas are all accessible at least by car, boat or on foot, which makes them vulnerable for GNSS interference. Helsinki and Kotka are additionally accessible by boat or swimming. They can be speculated by two interference scenarios where interference is done by privacy seeking citizens using in-car jammers or by professionals with powerful and (semi)portable equipment. This study does not make assumption of directed antenna since consumer-grade jammers do not usually have those. Therefore, the assumed results of professional interference should be considered as representative results but not entirely accurate since e. g. military-grade jammers usually have directional antennas (Kjellén, 2018).

Ylläs, Kolari

Ylläs fell hillshade

1 km

Figure 5. Ylläs research area presented as different visualizations with placement of transmitter (red dot). Upper left: topographic map of Ylläs, upper right: Aerial image of Ylläs, bottom: Hillshade with ASL values. Data source: NLS and Karttapaikka.

Ylläs research area in Lapland is located in the municipality of Kolari in the western part of Finnish Lapland. The specific location is the top of Ylläs fell at an elevation of 719 meters above sea level (Figure 5). Ylläs is a popular skiing destination for both domestic and foreign tourists and the Pallas-Ylläs National Park of which Ylläs belongs to, is also one of the most visited national parks in Finland. The location of the simulated jammer was in Ylläs fell in between ski slopes: the exact location in ETRS-TM35FIN is N 67° 33.847' E 24° 13.598'.

The top of Ylläs is reachable by car or snowmobile as well as by skis or foot. There are also many restaurants close to the top. Interference could be made in this area with in-car jammer by driving around the area or just by visiting restaurants with jammer device. Also, a jammer could be hidden to the area.

Seinäjoki

The Seinäjoki research area is located in the city of Seinäjoki west from the city centre near the Alajoki expanse. The research area was chosen to represent a flat area where signal could propagate freely. Seinäjoki area is fairly flat compared to the rest of the Finland. The research area in Alajoki expanse has lots of fields and is cultivated, but there are also some residential buildings nearby as can be seen in Figure 6. In this scenario jammer is positioned next to the train track that is used by long-distance trains. The simulated jammer was positioned in ETRS-TM35FIN coordinates of N 62° 46.925' E 22° 41.889'.

Seinäjoki DEM

1 km

Figure 6. Visualizations of Seinäjoki research area with placement of transmitter (red dot). Upper left: topographic map of Seinäjoki, upper right: Aerial image of Seinäjoki, bottom: DEM with ASL values. Data source: NLS and Karttapaikka.

Santalahti, Kotka

The Santalahti research area in Kotka represents an area that has both land and water aspects as it is used by leisure-time boatmen. This area is accessible by foot, car and boat. In this research area signal can propagate freely over the water. Right next to Santalahti area is located the Mussalo of Hamina-Kotka port, which is one of the busiest ports in Finland. The simulated jammer was located in ETRS-TM35FIN coordinates N 60° 26.095' E 26° 51.749'. The significant topographic characteristics in Santalahti are hills in nearby islands as well as in the north-western part of research area (Figure 7).

Santalahti DEM

1 km

Figure 7. Santalahti research area with different visualizations and placement of transmitter (red dot). Upper left: topographic map of Santalahti, upper right: Aerial image of Santalahti, bottom: DEM with ASL values. Data source: NLS and Karttapaikka.

Punavuori, Helsinki

An urban environment was chosen to highlight the effects of jamming in urban built-up area with high buildings. The Punavuori research area is located in the capital of Finland, Helsinki. Punavuori is densely built urban area that is accessible by car, foot and tram. The topography of Punavuori research area is quite flat, because the elevation difference in the whole DEM area compared to the sea level is 1–36 meters (Figure 9). Jamming scenario was simulated with the combination of DEM and OSM building data. The location of simulated jammer was in the middle of the Punavuorenkatu and Perämiehenkatu junction: the exact location in ETRS-TM35FIN is N 60° 09.605' E 24° 56.030'.

Figure 7. Punavuori DEM, DSM and background map with placement of simulated transmitter (red dot).

2.3 Methods

The workflow of data processing is presented in Figure 9 and the exact used functions are presented in the code for MATLAB signal propagation in Appendix 1. MATLAB provides RF Toolbox for designing, analyzing and modeling networks of radio frequency components (Mathworks, 2024). The used functions of this toolbox were from sub-toolbox Antenna Toolbox and its category RF Propagation. The main idea is to set a transmitter, i. e. simulated jammer, on chosen location in research area to visualize and calculate the propagation of jamming signal. This can be done with functions like *tx_site*, *coverage* and *rx_site*.

Figure 8. Flowchart explaining the process of calculating the path loss of jamming signal and creating a receiver site for jamming transmitter.

The whole process starts with picking the exact coordinates for research area and downloading the DEM raster of that exact area from Karttapaikka. To be able to use digital elevation data of NLS in MATLAB the DEM raster file has to be converted to DTED file format that the software is able to

use. DTED file format is a Digital Terrain Elevation Data format that is produced in three resolution levels and is authorized by the American office of Geomatics (NGA, 2024). The conversion of file format was done with ArcGIS PRO geoprocessing tool Raster to DTED with nearest resampling technique. All DEMs were converted to DTED level 2 which has spatial resolution of 30 meters. However, ArcGIS PRO claims that DTED level 2 could have resolution of 2 to 30 meters. By calculating the cell sizes of DTED file the spatial resolution is near 30 meters. The spatial resolution degrades from the original NLS data but the primary data has detailed topography data which should offer a suitable base for topography measurements even when resolution is compromised.

The data processing starts by defining the coordinates for transmitter, i. e. a place where the jammer would be located. The location of transmitter was chosen individually for every research area based on the assumption that the location would be easily accessed by the person who is creating the interference intentionally. Accessible location meant that every location of transmitter can be accessed by foot, car or other vehicle. All research areas were visually examined with the help of satellite images and by analyzing the topography with hill shading image to ensure the accessibility (Figures 6–9).

Transmitter is a simulated jammer with the same parameters that a jammer would, such as specified jamming frequency, antenna height (i. e. the height from the ground) and jamming power. The transmitter frequency of 1575.42 represents the Galileo's E1 and GPS's L1 signal frequency which are the most common targeted signals for jamming (see 2.4.3 and 2.4.4). This research simulates the use of commonly used, low-power (500 milliwatts to couple watts) jamming devices and high-power professionally used devices that can be freely bought online. The simulated transmitter powers are scaled to correspond the available low-power jammers (hundreds of milliwatts to couple watts) but also to demonstrate the effects of speculated powers of equipment that are used to create intended harm (multiple watts) (see 2.4.3). The 500 mW and 1 W jammers represent the consumer-grade jammers, even though one-watt-jammer would be on the end of the power scale of consumer devices. 5-watt and 40-watt jammers represent professional use of jamming devices. All of the jammer powers are speculated and chosen by the available data of sold jammers and speculations about the capacity of professional users.

Tx_site -function creates a radio frequency transmitter site for wanted location, antenna height, frequency and power. These all are vital arguments for jamming signals. The only changing variable for research areas was the location of transmitter and the simulated receiver matrix. Constant variables for every research area are listed in the Table 2.

Table 2. Constant variables for every study site.

Antenna height	1.5 m
Transmitter frequency	1575.42 MHz
Transmitter power	500 mW 1 W 5 W 40 W
Number of receivers (in the receiver matrix)	121

The constant variables were chosen to homogenize the research areas so they could be compared to each other. Antenna height of 1.5 meters represents the median height of a Finnish car and it is also a height where the jammer could be carried by person, such as in a backpack (Knaapi, 2017). The assumption is that the in-car jammer is used anywhere inside the car, even though in-car jammers are usually inserted to the cigarette lighter, which height is somewhere between one and one and half meters depending on the vehicle.

For simulating the physics of signal propagation, a propagation model must be chosen. Propagation model is an estimation of signal strengths with given parameters for a wireless system (Yun & Iskander, 2015). For this research the propagation model Longley-Rice was used for Ylläs, Seinäjoki and Santalahti research areas since it takes irregular terrain into account, is suitable for climate in Finland, antenna's horizontal polarization and after all suitable for satellite signal frequencies. The Longley-Rice model is based on the data collected in appropriate frequencies and antenna heights, specifically to frequencies between 40 MHz and 100 GHz, antenna heights between 0.5 meters and 3000 meters and distances between 1 and 2000 kilometers (Seybold, 2005). This model predicts the behaviour of electromagnetic radiation from the point of transmission over detailed terrain data. Other commonly used path loss model for modeling signal propagation over detailed terrain is Okumura-Hata model (Morong et al., 2019).

For urban research area, Punavuori, ray tracing propagation model was used to simulate the propagation of multipath signal in urban area. Ray tracing model provides estimates of path loss values from LOS or diffracted signals (Yun & Iskander, 2015). To simulate urban area that is susceptible for multipath with high buildings, the number of signal path reflections was 10, material for buildings and terrain concrete, and average number of degrees between launched rays was low. Other parameters were set as default.

The jamming scenario is visualized with coverage function that visualizes the power of interference and shows it in different colours on top of a base map. The visualized different colours indicate the expected signal strengths and in MATLAB's display are scaled between -120 and -5 decibel-milliwatts. Coverage function simulates jamming signal with the specified transmitter and its characteristics and chosen propagation model. The signal propagation in different topographies is presented in Figure 10 and 11 with different colours. Blue colour indicates -120 dBm power of expected power of jamming signal. Empty, terrain-coloured areas are areas that interference does not affect due to topography in visualized jamming scenario. As the Figure 10 also suggests jamming signal propagates over irregular terrain.

Figure 9. The display of MATLAB's site viewer. Jamming signal visualized over irregular Ylläs terrain.

Figure 10. Jamming signal visualized as different colours over Ylläs fell.

The functionality of MATLAB's coverage function was tested with transmitter locations outside the chosen study site to see if the results are congruent. Also, an amateur software, Radio Mobile, was used to see if the results between MATLAB and Radio Mobile were compatible. Radio Mobile is an open access, web-based software for predicting the performance of radio system (Radio Mobile, 2024). The same arguments except frequency for interference were used as in MATLAB's coverage function. Radio Mobile is created for and highly used by radio amateurs so it cannot be used to restricted (i. e. illegal to interfere) frequencies such as E1 and L1. Instead, a frequency of Galileo's E6 signal of 1278.75 MHz, was used. This frequency is not dedicated to GNSS alone exclusively but can also be used for example for TV signals (Morrison et al., 2021). The results in both software were similar between different tested study sites as Figure 12 shows. MATLAB seems to visualize the jamming signal as supposed to.

Figure 11. The comparison between Radio Mobile (A) and MATLAB (B) coverage function results with jamming of one microwatt in Ylläs fell. On the right are the used arguments for Radio Mobile. The other arguments but antenna height, frequency and power are by default.

After interference is visualized, it can be examined in the site viewer display of MATLAB (Figure 11 and 12). From the visualized jamming scenario, the topographic obstacles and their effect on signal propagation can be inspected. The workflow of steps after visualization are presented in Figure 13.

Figure 12. Flowchart explaining the process of signal propagation inspection.

From the area of interest, four obstacles were chosen to exemplify different topographic characteristics in the area. As Figure 14 illustrates the four chosen obstacles could be for example the fells and slopes of Ylläs. The receiver matrix was positioned to the areas of interest which represented different topographic characteristics of the research area.

Figure 13. Jamming signal visualized on top of Ylläs fell and its neighbouring fells. Orange arrows point to areas where topography affects the expected power of jamming signal by attenuating, blocking or directing the signal.

In order to calculate the effects of topography a receiver matrix can be simulated to the research area (see Fig 22, appendix 2). The receivers in MATLAB are imagined devices that calculate the received power of satellite signal. The purpose of the receiver matrix is to calculate the received power values within the receiver site to see if the power of jamming signal varies between obstacles. The path loss calculations were made to see if the received jamming signal power is decreased by the topographic obstacles by calculating the received power before and after obstacle.

A receiver matrix can be computed with *rx_site* function that places receivers to the area with specified factors such as antenna height and receiver sensitivity. MATLAB cannot sufficiently compute matrix receiver for the whole DEM (6 x 6 km) area. To improve computational efficiency of MATLAB the size of receiver matrix was kept small and the receiver site was repositioned to the areas of interest instead of calculating a matrix of thousands of receivers on the DEM area. Therefore, the received power of simulated jamming signal was calculated with a matrix of 121 receivers on chosen 1 km by 1 km area.

The step size (i. e. distance) between receivers was 10 meters so signal would not significantly attenuate between receivers and affect the calculations. The received power, i. e. path loss, was tabulated for the chosen four receivers. Path loss values can be viewed with command *pathloss* and *pal_info* (see Appendix 1).

The assumption is that jammers do not have special antennas. Instead, the used antenna parameter is an isotropic antenna which is an idealized antenna that measures radiation from every direction (Ward et al., 2017). The consumer-grade jammers most likely have the antenna and receiver unit very close to each other and the cable between them is short which results to zero or miniscule loss of power (Poutanen, 2016). Therefore, transmitter antenna and receiver antenna gain as well as loss were not specified in this study.

3 RESULTS

The areas of GNSS jamming scenarios varied by the transmitter power. The most effective interference is created with high-power jammer. Significant is that in all research areas low-power jammer of 500 milliwatts was able to create interference around the jammer even in varying topographies. Table 3 presents the interference areas of different research areas and their jamming scenarios. It must be noted that the maximum area of interference of 36 km² is limited by the size of DEMs which is the computational limit of this method. The values are based on visual approximation from Figures 16 and 18–20. In real environment jamming signal is able to propagate further than the size of DEMs but MATLAB cannot consistently visualize signal further. The speculated whole areas of interference are visualized in Figures 23–25 (see Appendices 4–6). The visualized whole areas are maximum areas that MATLAB is able to visualize jamming signals on.

Table 3. Interference areas of GNSS jamming scenarios.

Research area	500 mW	1 W	5 W	40 W	Distinctive feature
Ylläs	24 km ²	30 km ²	34 km ²	35.5 km ²	Jammer on top of a fell
Seinäjoki	36 km ²	36 km ²	36 km ²	36 km ²	Expanse
Santalahti	20 km ²	23 km ²	36 km ²	36 km ²	Water
Punavuori	21 km ²	21 km ²	21 km ²	21 km ²	Buildings and multipath

The visualization of GNSS jamming signals was successful. The coverage function visualizes the jamming scenarios in a scale of thirteen power levels from -120 to -5 dBm's. All jamming signal visualization results are presented in the size of DEM files (6 km by 6 km). Thirteen colours represent the expected power of signal which is in GNSS jamming scenarios the expected strength of interference. The areas that are coloured blue or other colour, are under interference. The blue colour in visualizations indicate the interference of -120 decibel-milliwatts, which is more than the average received power -130 decibel-milliwatts of actual satellite signal. Other colours of power scale (e. g. yellow and red) indicate strong interference.

In MATLAB simulation, topographic characters were able to hinder the interference even though the jamming power was increased. The jamming signal was the strongest (colours green, yellow and red) in areas where there were no objects to block or hinder the signal propagation. Jamming signal

propagated systematically in the area and topography affected the received power by attenuating, but not blocking, the jamming signal.

The stronger the expected GNSS jamming signal strength is, the more it affects satellite positioning. In the areas that GNSS jamming signal is able to cover the PNT services are most likely hindered or degraded. The actual effect of jamming signals depends on the capabilities of receivers, such as car navigator or other device used to GNSS services. The most paralyzing effect interference has on critical applications of GNSS, such as electricity transmission networks timing data.

As expected, the power of received jamming signal varied by the distance to the transmitter in all research areas. The strongest interference was received next to the transmitter in every study site as free space loss propagation model suggests. The signal attenuates as a function of distance and frequency (see 1.2). MATLAB's Longley-Rice propagation model assumes LOS conditions and calculates path loss between two points.

The receiver matrix calculates values for jamming signal propagation by distance but not the effect of topographies. Four receivers were placed to areas where topographic obstacles would affect the received power in every area. The varying transmitter power and the effect of topographic obstacles were calculated in every research area. It was found that MATLAB's pathloss-function gives the same received power values even though transmitter power is increased from milliwatts to watts. Pathloss-function does not take the transmitter power into account. Since the received power does not change, it suggests that MATLAB's Longley-Rice or Raytracing propagation models do not have transmitter power as a parameter. The documentation of the path loss function does not mention the effect of power as a parameter. However, the assumption for this study was to test the capabilities of RF Toolbox functions, and assumption was that it could take transmitter power into account even though it is not clearly specified in the documentation. Due to this limitation exact values of path loss for exact locations cannot be calculated.

Figure 15 portrays the chosen placements of four receivers in Santalahti area. Table 4 presents the notes on chosen receivers and their received power. Four receivers were placed in every research area but are not presented as figures or tables since the topography nor transmitter power doesn't have an effect to the received values, i. e. the chosen receivers do not give new information about the effects of topography. The received powers were in line with free space path loss formula and expected received power for different distances in research areas can be calculated with Formula 1 (see 1.2).

Satellite Image of Santalahti Research Area
With Placement of Transmitter and Chosen Receivers

Figure 14. Chosen receivers and transmitter in Santalahti. Satellite image: Earthstar Geographics.

Table 4. Santalahti jamming scenario

Receiver id	Distance to the transmitter	Received power	Object	Notes
Rf_1	1 km	-123 dB	9-meter-hill	
Rf_2	4.5 km	-161 dB		
Rf_3	400 m	-98 dB		Longley-Rice model is designed for >1 km distances
Rf_4	2 km	-127.7 dB	hill	

With this MATLAB method, the effect of topography cannot be proven with precise values in decibels but the estimated received signal strength can be visualized. Interference, i. e. the received power in chosen receivers, remained the same due to the propagation model that cannot calculate path

loss with varying transmitter power. The received powers were in line with free space path loss formula in all areas and signal attenuated as a function of distance (see 1.2).

The received power after jamming effecting objects were calculated after object in receiver. The results are presented in decibels which is commonly used unit for path loss values. Coverage of the jamming signal is in decibel-milliwatts since it presents the signal strengths, not singular values for received power. Decibel-milliwatt values represent the power that can be expected to be received from transmitter, which is why the interference can be visualized as different powers in research area.

Ylläs

The interference scenario in Ylläs fell is presented in Figure 16. The most effective and large interference was created with the 40 W jammer. Topography affected the efficiency of the jamming when the power of jamming was low but interference power over 5 W was able to affect almost the whole DEM (6 x 6 km area).

Ylläs GNSS jamming scenario

Figure 15. Ylläs jamming scenario visualized on top of a satellite image with different jamming powers: A) 500 mW, B) 1 W, C) 5 W & D) 40 W. (Source of satellite image: Maxar & Earthstar Geographics.)

The area of interference for 500 mW was approximately 24 km² and for 1 W 30 km². 5-watt and 40-watt interference were able to cover almost the whole DEM area of 36 km² without the northern slope of Kellostapuli fell. The approximate interference area for 5 W was 34 km² and for 40 W 35.5 km². The speculated area of the whole interference is presented in the Figure 23 (in Appendix 4).

The power varies within the area due to topography with the strongest interference right next to transmitter and the tops of nearby fells Keskinenlaki and Kellostapuli in the north (Figure 17). The areas that were not affected by the jamming scenario were for example the slope of Kellostapuli and for low-power interference the western parts of Ylläs fell. There are areas that have strong expected power level of jamming signal such as the eastern parts of Ylläs fell. These are visualized as light green and yellow areas. The jamming signal is directed to propagate more freely on these areas due to the height differences (see Figure 5). The height difference between the top of Ylläs fell and the eastern parts of the research area is approximately 460 meters. The jamming signal is able to slide down the slope of Ylläs fell to lower regions without topographic obstacles.

Figure 16. Jamming signal propagates over Keskinenlaki and Kellostapuli effectively.

As Ylläs research area is used mostly for leisure-time activities, jamming would affect the devices in the area that use GNSS services, such as mobile phones and card readers in restaurants. This could mean errors in navigation information and unavailability of precise location data. Unavailable

location data would for example unavailable access to the social media geotags or unavailable routing information for navigators for off-piste skiers causing potential hazard risks. Noteworthy is that jamming that would be made from higher elevation will propagate more than jamming that is done from lower locations. Signal propagates freely from high vertical propagations because it has less obstacles. In Ylläs area there are obstacles, like other fells, that hinder the jamming signal propagation. If the jammer would have a directed antenna, the fringe area, like Kellostapuli fell, would be avoided and interference would be more effective.

Seinäjäki

The interference scenario in Seinäjoki research area is presented in Figure 18. All tested power options were able to cover the whole area of DEM. This is different compared to other research areas where the lowest jamming signal power, 500 milliwatts, did not propagate as freely.

Seinäjäki GNSS jamming scenario

Figure 17. Seinäjoki jamming scenario visualized on top of a satellite image with different jamming powers: A: 500 mW, B: 1 W, C: 5 W & D: 40 W. (Source of satellite image: Maxar & Earthstar Geographics.)

Increase in jammer power made the geographical area of strong jamming signal larger. Map D in Figure 18 illustrated the strength of expected jamming signal which is at least -70 dBm in the whole DEM area.

This is almost twice as strong as the received satellite signal. In other research areas this strong signal is limited to smaller areas.

The site where the simulated jammer was placed is flat and has height differences of only 40 meters. The results from this study site highlight the effect of topography: signal propagates freely when there are no significant topographic obstacles. The simulated jammer is placed next to a train track. Due to the high speed of passing trains, jamming wouldn't exactly affect the trains and their functioning, but jamming would affect the nearby residential area and PNT services, such as navigation between locations, utilized in the area. Figure 24 illustrates the whole speculated area of interference in Seinäjoki research area. (see Appendix 5).

Santalahti

The interference scenario in Santalahti is presented in Figure 19. The most effective and large interference was created with the 40 W jammer. Topography affected the efficiency of the jamming when the power of jamming was low.

The whole interference area grew when jamming power increased from milliwatts to watts (Figure 19). Noteworthy is that low-power jammer is able to create interference. Figure 19 shows the interference in 6 x 6 km area, but it is noteworthy to say that the interference spreads to larger area (see Figure 25 in Appendix 6).

Santalahti GNSS jamming scenario

Figure 18. Santalahti jamming scenario visualized on top of a satellite image with different jamming powers: A) 500 mW, B) 1 W, C) 5 W & D) 40 W. (Source of satellite image: Maxar & Earthstar Geographics.)

The area of interference for 500 mW was approximately 20 km² and for 1 W 23 km². 5-watt and 40-watt interference were able to cover the whole DEM area of 36 km². The speculated area of interference is presented in the Figure 25 (see appendix 3). The main limiting objects in Santalahti

were the small hills on the west side of the transmitter, but all in all jamming signal propagates freely in the area-

Jamming hinders the GNSS services in the Santalahti area significantly. The area is in leisure boating use and navigation plotters will not have sufficient connection to GNSS services leading to the unavailable positioning data. This would mean problems to the boatsmen who rely on electronic devices on routing and navigation on waters. To be prepared for jamming situations and be sure of own safety, the Finnish Coast Guard recommends to always carry physical paper maps onboard (Saarinen, 2022).

There is also one of the biggest ports of Finland right next to the jamming scenario area, which infrastructure and vessels would be affected strongly. This would be serious threat to the security of supply of Finland as this port is critical infrastructure for Finland.

Punavuori

The interference scenario in Punavuori research area is presented in the Figure 20. Jamming signal propagates in the limits of obstacles by getting blocked by buildings, but in street canyons signal propagates further. The interference area for different simulated powers of jamming is approximately 21 km². Due to buildings the jamming signal does not propagate further with increased power and the area of interference stays the same. The expected power of jamming signal changes according to jammer's power.

Punavuori GNSS jamming scenario

Figure 19. Punavuori jamming scenario visualized on top of a satellite image and OSM buildings with different jamming powers: A) 500 mW, B) 1 W, C) 5 W & D) 40 W. (Source of satellite image: Maxar & Earthstar Geographics.)

In urban areas, such as Punavuori jamming is limited besides topography also by buildings when the jamming scenario defines the horizontal height of propagation. The area of interference is significantly smaller than in unbuilt areas where jamming signal propagated almost to the whole area even with low-power jamming (Figure 21). The difficulties of urban areas are e. g. multipath due to signals reflections from different surfaces. Because of the limiting factor of vertical blocks in Punavuori area the power loss between objects is not calculated. The only limiting factor for signal propagation is therefore buildings which prevent the spreading of jamming signal, i. e. jamming signal propagates to the nearby area from transmitter until it is blocked by a building.

Punavuori research area

Figure 20. Punavuori research area with 40 W jamming. The jamming signal is effectively blocked by buildings to a small area.

There are multiple applications of GNSS services in urban areas are diverse user groups. In Punavuori research area there are also authorities present, such as police forces and the Customs in port areas.

Fortunately built area is efficient in blocking signal by providing a challenging area for signal propagation in normal satellite signal situations. There are areas that have low positioning accuracy due to the multipath. Nevertheless, the local impact on GNSS services is as lethal as it is in every other area.

4 DISCUSSION

In all researched areas GNSS jamming has paralyzing or at least hindering effect on GNSS data availability and accuracy with the simulated powers. In this study 500-milliwatt interference had distinct effect on different areas covering more than 20 km² in each area. One-watt jamming signal was able to cover almost 36 km² areas in all researched topographies without obstacles. This highlights the significant impact of consumer-grade jammers and the need to educate citizens on the vast effects of seemingly unarmful privacy seeking by hiding own location information with in-car jammers. It must be noted that education and attention on this matter might also encourage to use jammers.

Topographic characters had impact on the propagation of jamming signal. Obstacles, such as hills, were able to attenuate jamming signal when the transmitted power was low. This indicates that consumer-grade low-power jammers have remarkable effect, but their effects and interference's spatial impact are hindered by topography. 5-watt and 40-watt interference were able to affect the whole research areas with small fringe areas in Ylläs. Buildings in urban area able to block and direct the jamming signal as expected.

Previous research has concentrated on to different jammers, their characteristics and the effect of jamming on positioning accuracy (Morong et al., 2019; Axell et al., 2019; Morrison et al., 2023). This research offers new information about the jamming signal propagation in different environments that has not been researched in this manner, so it is quite difficult to discuss with previous studies.

Because precise values for path loss in exact locations cannot be calculated, this method should be used as a representative and guiding method for visualizing GNSS jamming signals in different topographies. With the size limitations of DEM of NLS this method is exclusive for the area of DEM

and therefore gives an example of local impact of topographic characteristics against GNSS jamming signals.

4.1 The impact of topography

Topography affected the propagation of jamming signals in jamming simulations similarly as it would in real environment. The defined height of 1.5 meters, however, might create areas where MATLAB shows empty areas where jamming would in real environment be effective since signals propagate freely to all directions and not as strictly horizontal phenomenon as simulated in this study. Horizontal height and horizontal propagation were defined in this study to define topography as a limitative factor for MATLAB signal propagation.

It must be noted that the methods used in this study are able to highlight the effect of topographic obstacles and irregular terrain and this method is suitable especially for areas with elevation differences. However, in real physical environment there would be multiple obstacles for GNSS jamming signal alongside terrain, such as buildings and trees. To improve these simulations a point cloud data, that includes other environment's characteristics, like trees and buildings, could be used. Point cloud data could be produced with LiDAR scanning and from the point cloud data a surface model of the area could be generated. With point cloud data the real environments could be further studied to simulate jamming in different environments by their unique characteristics.

In unbuilt environment there was only one area, the northern slope of Kellostapuli fell in Ylläs research area, where interference didn't have effect on. In Alajoki plains in Seinäjoki research area jamming signal propagated freely to every direction. Topography is significant hindering or blocking factor when signal propagates.

When assessing the vulnerability of different areas, the results confirm that topography offers cover against jamming signals. Flat terrain, such as Seinäjoki expanse and sea area in Santalahti, is defenceless against interference. Areas with more terrain characteristics offer more cover with obstacles that block the signal propagation. The buildings in Punavuori research area were able to effectively block the jamming signal to a limited area of buildings. However, the impact jamming has on urban areas is severe. Punavuori research area is residential area with lots of population and different infrastructures. Even though the effective area of jamming is fairly small compared to other research areas the impact on GNSS services is as effective as in other areas.

The Ylläs DEM was the oldest laser scanned area and it was updated in 2015. Temporal resolution could be better in this dataset (table 5, appendix 3). However, DEM takes topography into account and ignores terrains other aspects such as forest canopy or buildings, thus topography hasn't changed in the research areas between the years significantly. The land uplift phenomenon increases the height elevation in all research areas some millimetres per year. The uplift rate related to the yearly sea level rise varies between regions in Finland and is at the most approximately 8 millimetres (Poutanen, 2024). The increases for height elevation would not make a difference in such small research areas on signal propagation and signal would propagate similarly with newer elevation data. Land uplift could however affect the accuracy of EUREF-FIN coordinates and the N2000 reference system used by DEMs.

4.2 The usability of MATLAB's RF Toolbox

The chosen method, MATLAB's RF propagation-toolbox, is suitable to simulating jamming signals in different topographies when exact values of received power in specific locations are not expected. The power of jamming signal (i. e. transmitter power) does not affect the received values in receivers since it is not a factor in MATLAB's path loss function. However, this method is applicable to visualize expected interference signal strengths in different topographies. MATLAB simulates jamming signal as it should by computing the signal as free space loss propagation formula suggests: the signal attenuates by the distance and the interference is highest near the transmitter. Obstacles affect the propagation of jamming signal by blocking or attenuating the interference when horizontal height for jamming signal is defined. The impact of topography is present especially in areas with significant height differences. In urban areas built obstacles hinder signal propagation along with topography.

When using this method, it must be noted that DEM does not take any other terrain characteristics than elevation into account. MATLAB does not accept any other file formats than DTED file format as custom terrain data, so point cloud data cannot be used. The conversion of a point cloud data to DTED file would simplify the heights and singular objects, such as buildings or trees, and they would be fitted to the elevation data. The conversion simplifies height differences and classification of the point cloud data would be a compromise between emphasizing elevation or singular obstacle heights.

DTED file also has limitations with spatial resolution as it only offers 30-meter-resolution even though the NLS data is significantly better. Other method for simulating jamming scenarios could

be for example using horizontal visibility analysis with the point cloud data or to use point cloud data with Python libraries and functions. However, at the moment there are no stable and suitable Python libraries for this kind of research. In the future the GNSS jamming simulators might be able to simulate the topographies of different areas if they accept other base maps. For example, Spirent's simulators base map is the OSM, which doesn't take topography into account.

The size of the DEM also limits visualization. If the NLS's DEM would be bigger or MATLAB would be able to use multiple DEMs for terrain data, a larger simulation for jamming scenarios could be visualized. Also, the research areas are not located in the middle of DEMs, which limits the size of reliable interference area. If the research areas would be situated in the middle of the DEMs the spatial accuracy of interference could be increased, but this research based on interesting topographies and was not made in the limits of available data. The limitations of combined available data and NLS's data make reliable and coherent visualization impracticable. The default DEM data provided by MATLAB has faults, such as empty areas, and when combined with NLS's data the visualization is not consistent (see e. g. appendix 4).

MATLAB has limitations with the size of receiver matrix, which means that receiver matrix cannot be computed for the whole interference area at once. To better the fluency of calculating path losses the limitations should be removed by bettering the computing capabilities of receiver matrix.

MATLAB has multiple parameters for functions, and it provides possibilities to simulate interference in different scenarios with other frequencies and transmitter powers. The used parameters for RF Toolbox functions weren't specified for every research area locally but instead a generalized view was conducted. For example, propagation models were used with mostly default parameters such as 'continental-temperate' radio climate zone. Propagation models could be further specified to take local characteristics into account, such as by defining the expected level of multipath by rescaling the time variability tolerance level.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This research gives information and an overview about topographic effects on GNSS jamming signals that present GNSS simulators are not able to produce. GNSS interference simulators cannot exemplify the effects of terrain and topography and this research and its results are a step closer to simulating the effect of jamming in different environments. Research on GNSS jamming signals is important to national security of Finland. GNSS jamming scenarios provide data of vulnerable topographies. The results of this study also prove the importance of the power levels of jammers when low-power jammers can have significant spatial effects.

GNSS services are vulnerable and threatened by interference, especially by jamming. The impact of jamming is severe for PNT services. In flat terrain, such as Seinäjoki research area or sea areas in Santalahti research area, jamming signal can propagate freely and hinder or block for example navigation services. Jamming can have lethal effects on the critical infrastructures and spatially significant jamming can be created with low-power jammers. The impact of high-power jamming devices used by e. g. armed forces are enormous.

This simulation study can be conducted to other areas with the used methods. With this method interference can be exemplified with simple functions to visually demonstrate the spatial effectivity of GNSS jamming. It is noteworthy that the simulations cannot accurately mimic real environment because MATLAB cannot read detailed point cloud data. The simulation results can be viewed and inspected without specific knowledge about GNSS since the results are visually presented in an understandable way. Visual analysis can be done without specific knowledge on topic. This simulation study provides information about the usability of MATLAB's RF propagation toolbox and its usability on simulating different power GNSS jamming signals on different topographies.

These simulations give an overview to the spatial effectivity of GNSS jamming signals when terrain and jammer characteristics are defined. To research this topic further, the different power jamming scenarios could be simulated to different areas in and outside Finland with suitable terrain data. With this method the simulation of jamming with different powers can be repeated on other areas. The provided code can be adapted to different areas with simple alterations for e. g. to tx_site-function (appendix 1). The GNSS jamming simulations that were conducted in this study could also be used to speculate and analyse the effect of GNSS jamming on strategically important areas, such as airports or military areas, by placing the transmitter to strategic areas.

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6 REFERENCES

- AARTOS (Mar 2024). Systems and versions AARTOS Drone Detection System. Retrieved from <https://drone-detection-system.com/aartos-dds/systems-versions/>
- Act on Electronic Communications Services 917/2014. Issued 7.11.2014 in Helsinki. Retrieved from https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2014/en20140917_20201207.pdf
- Alén-Savikko, A. (2019). Satelliittipaikannuksen häirintä lainsäädännön kohinassa. *Lakimies*, 3–4, 240–263. <https://www.edilex.fi/lakimies/198840001.pdf>
- Ashour, I., Tokhey, M. E., Mogahed, Y., & Ragheb, A. (2022). Performance of global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) in absence of GPS observations. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2021.09.016>
- Arribas, J., Vilà-Valls, J., Ramos, A., Fernández-Prades, C., & Closas, P. (2019). Air traffic control radar interference event in the Galileo E6 band: Detection and localization. *NAVIGATION: Journal of the Institute of Navigation*, 66(3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/navi.310>
- Ávila Rodríguez, J. A. (2008). On Generalized Signal Waveforms for Satellite Navigation. Doctoral Thesis. University FAF Munich. 408 p., p. 12-13. <https://d-nb.info/1066345600/34>
- Ávila Rodríguez, J. A. (2011). *Galileo Signal Plan* ESA Navipedia. Retrieved from https://gssc.esa.int/navipedia/index.php?title=Galileo_Signal_Plan
- Axell, E., Eklöf, F. M., Johansson, P., Alexandersson, M., & Akos, D. M. (2015). Jamming Detection in GNSS Receivers: Performance Evaluation of Field Trials. *NAVIGATION: Journal of the Institute of Navigation*, 62(1), 73-82. <https://doi.org/10.1002/navi.74>
- Bhuiyan, M. Z. H., Kuusniemi, H., Söderholm, S., & Airos, E. (2014). The Impact of Interference on GNSS Receiver Observables – A Running Digital Sum Based Simple Jammer Detector *Radioengineering*, 23(3), 898-906. https://www.radioeng.cz/fulltexts/2014/14_03_0898_0906.pdf
- Bingen, K. A., Johnson, K., Young, M., & Raymond, J. (2023). *Space Threat Assessment 2023*. Retrieved from https://csis-website-prod.s3.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/2023-04/230414_Bingen_Space_Assessment.pdf?VersionId=oMsUS8MupLbZi3BISPrqPCKd5jDejZnJ
- Borio, D., Guasch, J. F., & O'Driscoll, C. (2013). Characterization of GNSS Jammers. *Coordinates*, 4(5), 8–16. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC82267>
- Cai, C., Gao, Y., Pan, L., & Zhu, J. (2015). Precise point positioning with quad-constellations: GPS, BeiDou, GLONASS and Galileo. *Advances in Space Research*, 56(1), 133–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2015.04.001>
- Coercive Measures Act 2011/806. Issued in Helsinki 22.7.2011. Retrieved from https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110806_20131146.pdf
- Council Decision 1104/2011/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the rules for access to the public regulated service provided by the global navigation satellite system established under the Galileo programme *OJ L 287*, 4.11.2011, p. 1–8
- Choy, S., Kuckartz, J., Dempster, A. G., Rizos, C., & Higgins, M. (2017). GNSS satellite-based augmentation systems for Australia. *GPS Solutions*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-016-0569-2>
- Dabove, P., Di Pietra, V., & Piras, M. (2020). GNSS Positioning Using Mobile Devices with the Android Operating System. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(4), 220. <https://www.mdpi.com/2220-9964/9/4/220>
- Das, N. K. (2005). Antennas and Radiation. In W.-K. Chen (Ed.), *The Electrical Engineering Handbook* (1 ed., pp. 1227). Elsevier Science & Technology.

- Defmin, The Ministry of Defence (2022). Defence budget for 2023 continues to strengthen defence capability. Retrieved from https://www.defmin.fi/en/topical/press_releases_and_news/press_release_archive/2022/defence_budget_for_2023_continues_to_strengthen_defence_capability.13053.news#d65ac604
- de Paula, E. R., Martinon, A. R. F., Carrano, C., Moraes, A. O., Neri, J. A. C. F., Cecatto, J. R., Abdu, M. A., Neto, A. C., Monico, J. F. G., da Costa Silva, W., Vani, B. C., Batista, I. S., Mendes, O., de Souza, J. R., & Silva, A. L. A. (2022). Solar Flare and Radio Burst Effects on GNSS Signals and the Ionosphere During September 2017. *Radio Science*, 57(10), e2021RS007418. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021RS007418>
- Defraigne, P., & Baire, Q. (2011). Combining GPS and GLONASS for time and frequency transfer. *Advances in Space Research*, 47(2), 265-275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2010.07.003>
- Dominy, N. J., & Duncan, B. W. (2001). GPS and GIS Methods in an African Rain Forest: Applications to Tropical Ecology and Conservation. *Ecology and Society*, 5(2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-00282-050206>
- Dovis, F. (2015). *GNSS Interference Threats and Countermeasures* Artech House.
- Dovis, F., Musumeci, L., Motella, B., & Falletti, E. (2015). Classification of Interfering Sources and Analysis of the Effects on GNSS Receivers. In *GNSS Interference Threats and Countermeasures*. Artech House.
- Directive 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on the harmonisation of the laws of the Member States relating to the making available on the market of radio equipment and repealing Directive 1999/5/EC Text with EEA relevance, 2014/53/EU Cong. Rec. (2014). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32014L0053>
- EC, European Commission (Jan 2024a). Galileo system. EU Space Policy. Retrieved from https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/eu-space-policy/galileo/galileo-system_en
- ECC, the Electronic Communications Committee (2013). ECC Recommendation (04)01. Retrieved from <https://docdb.cept.org/download/1875>
- Elango, A., Ujan, S., & Ruotsalainen, L. (2022a). *Disruptive GNSS Signal detection and classification at different Power levels Using Advanced Deep-Learning Approach* International Conference on Localization and GNSS (ICL-GNSS), Tampere, Finland. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9797026>
- Elango, A., Al-Tahmeesschi, A., Saukkoriipi, M., Malmivirta, T. & L. Ruotsalainen (2022b). Protecting GNSS Against Intentional Interference. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2208.11555v1.pdf>
- ESA, the European Space Agency (Dec 2023). Who's involved in Galileo. Retrieved from https://www.esa.int/Applications/Navigation/Galileo/Who_s_involved_in_Galileo
- EUSPA, The European Union Agency for the Space Programme (Nov 2023a). What is GNSS? Retrieved from https://www.euspa.europa.eu/european-space/eu-space-programme/what-gnss_30.10.
- EUSPA (Nov 2023b). What is EGNOS? Retrieved from <https://www.euspa.europa.eu/european-space/egnoss/what-egnoss>
- Falco, G., Pini, M., & Marucco, G. (2017). Loose and Tight GNSS/INS Integrations: Comparison of Performance Assessed in Real Urban Scenarios. *Sensors*, 17(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s17020255>
- Fairheller, S., & Terrill, B. (2017). Regional SATNAV Systems. In E. Kaplan & C. Hegarty (Eds.), *Understanding GPS/GNSS: Principles and Applications* (third ed., pp. 1017). Artech House.
- FCC, Federal Communications Commission (USA) (2020). Jammer Enforcement. <https://www.fcc.gov/general/jammer-enforcement>
- Gao, W., Gao, C., & Pan, S. (2015). A method of GPS/BDS/GLONASS combined RTK positioning for middle-long baseline with partial ambiguity resolution. *Survey Review*, 49(354). <https://doi.org/10.1179/1752270615Y.0000000047>
- Genova, J. (2018). *Electronic Warfare Signal Processing*. Artech House.

- Greenemeier, L. (2016). GPS and the World's First "Space War". *Scientific American*, Springer Nature. <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/gps-and-the-world-s-first-space-war/>
- Groves, P. D. (2013). *Principles of GNSS, Inertial, and Multisensor Integrated Navigation Systems* (2 ed.). Artech House.
- GSC, European GNSS Service Centre (2020). *SAR/Galileo Service Definition Document*. Retrieved from <https://www.gsc-europa.eu/sites/default/files/sites/all/files/Galileo-SAR-SDD.pdf>
- GSC (Dec 2023). What is Galileo HAS? <https://www.gsc-europa.eu/galileo/services/galileo-high-accuracy-service-has>
- Hadas, T., Kazmierski, K., & Sośnica, K. (2019). Performance of Galileo-only dual-frequency absolute positioning using the fully serviceable Galileo constellation. *GPS Solutions*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-019-0900-9>
- Halminen, L. (2024). Onko Itämerta vaivaavien GPS-häiriöiden takana venäläinen satelliittien häirintälaitte? *Verkkouutiset*. Retrieved from <https://www.verkkouutiset.fi/a/onko-itamerta-vaivaavien-gps-hairioiden-takana-venalainen-satelliittien-hairintalaitte/#d3eedc17>
- Harrison, T., Johnson, K., Roberts, T. G., Bergethon, M., & Coultrup, A. (2019). *Space Threat Assessment 2019*. CSIS. <https://aerospace.csis.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/SpaceThreatAssessment2019-compressed.pdf>
- Heng, L., Work, D. B., & Gao, G. X. (2013). Cooperative GNSS Authentication: Reliability from Unreliable Peers. *Inside GNSS*, 8(5), 70–75. <https://insidegnss.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/SEPOCT13-HENG.pdf>
- Hägglblom, R. (2024). Sweden. In B. Ottosson & K. Pallin (Eds.), *Western Military Capability in Northern Europe 2023 –Part 1: National Capabilities*. Swedish Defence Research Agency. <https://www.foi.se/en/foi/reports/report-summary.html?reportNo=FOI-R--5527--SE>
- Hätäkeskuslaitos. (2022). *GPS-häiriöillä ei ole ollut suurta vaikutusta hätäpuheluiden paikantamisessa*. Retrieved from <https://112.fi/-/gps-hairioilla-ei-ole-ollut-suurta-vaikutusta-hatapuheluiden-paikantamisessa>
- IAC, Information and Analytical navigation Center (Russia) (Nov 2023). About GLONASS. Retrieved from https://glonass-iac.ru/en/about_glonass/
- ISRO, Indian Space Research Organisation. (Nov 2023). *Space Infrastructure: Navigation*. Retrieved from https://www.isro.gov.in/FAQ_Navigation.html
- ITU, the International Telecommunication Union (2019). Calculation of free-space attenuation. In Recommendation ITU-R P.525-4. Geneva.
- ITU (Jan 2024). About International Telecommunication Union (ITU). Retrieved from <https://www.itu.int/en/about/Pages/default.aspx>
- Jafarnia-Jahromi, A., Daneshmand, S., & G. Lachapelle (2013). 4 th International Colloquium on Scientific and Fundamental Aspects of the Galileo Programme. European Space Agency, Prague, 4-6 December 2013. University of Calgary. https://schulich.ucalgary.ca/labs/position-location-and-navigation/files/position-location-and-navigation/jafarnia2013_conference.pdf
- Jafarnia-Jahromi, A., Broumandan, A., Daneshmand, S., & Lachapelle, G. (2015). Vulnerability Analysis of Civilian L1/E1 GNSS Signals against Different Types of Interference. Proceedings of the 28th International Technical Meeting of the Satellite Division of The Institute of Navigation, Tampa.
- Jammertest (Mar 2024). About. Retrieved from <https://jammertest.no/about-2/>
- Jones, M. (2011). The Civilian Battlefield -Protecting GNSS Receivers from Interference and Jamming. *Inside GNSS*. <https://www.insidegnss.com/auto/marapr11-Jones.pdf>
- Jonsson, M. (2024). Finland. In B. Ottosson & K. Pallin (Eds.), *Western Military Capability in Northern Europe 2023 –Part 1: National Capabilities*. Swedish Defence Research Agency. <https://www.foi.se/en/foi/reports/report-summary.html?reportNo=FOI-R--5527--SE>

- Kaasalainen, S., Mäkelä, M., Saajasto, M., Kirkko-Jaakkola, M., & Kuusniemi, H. (2021). *Selvitys GNSS-palvelujen tarjonnasta ja toiminnasta*.
https://www.maanmittauslaitos.fi/sites/maanmittauslaitos.fi/files/GNSS_selvitys_loppuraportti.pdf
- Kaplan, E. (2017). Introduction: GNSS Overview. In E. D. Kaplan & C. Hegarty (Eds.), *Understanding GPS/GNSS: Principles and Applications* (third ed., pp. 1017). Artech House.
- Katsigianni, G., Loyer, S., & Perosanz, F. (2019a). PPP and PPP-AR Kinematic Post-Processed Performance of GPS-Only, Galileo-Only and Multi-GNSS. *Remote Sensing*, *11*(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11212477>
- Katsigianni, G., Loyer, S., Perosanz, F., Mercier, F., Zajdel, R., & Sošnica, K. (2019b). Improving Galileo orbit determination using zero-difference ambiguity fixing in a Multi-GNSS processing. *Advances in Space Research*, *63*(9).
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2018.08.035>
- Kjellén, J. (2018). *Russian Electronic Warfare -The Role of Electronic Warfare in the Russian Armed Forces* (FOI-R--4625--SE). Swedish Defence Research Agency. Retrieved from <https://www.foi.se/rest-api/report/FOI-R--4625--SE>
- Knaapi, J. (2017). *Suomessa tarjolla olevan henkilöautokaluston analysointi*. 21 p. Turku University of Applied Sciences.
- Ko, K.-S. (2010). A Basic Study on the Jamming Mechanisms and Characteristics against GPS/GNSS Based on Navigation Warfare. *Journal of Navigation and Port Research International Edition*, *34*(2), 97-103.
<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=41714ccc23b508eadfecc2a1258f8cef8201afe1>
- Kosola, J., & Jokinen, J. (2004). *Elektroninen sodankäynti: osa 1 – taistelun viides dimensio*. Maanpuolustuskorkeakoulun Tekniikan laitos. <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2020040610543>
- Kraus, T., Bauernfeind, R., & Eissfeller, B. (2011). *Survey of In-Car Jammers - Analysis and Modeling of the RF Signals and IF Samples (Suitable for Active Signal Cancelation)* 24th International Technical Meeting of the Satellite Division of The Institute of Navigation, Portland. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320907305_Survey_of_In-Car_Jammers_-_Analysis_and_Modeling_of_the_RF_Signals_and_IF_Samples_Suitable_for_Active_Signal_Cancelation
- Kuusniemi, H., Airos, E., Bhuyian, M. Z. H., & Kröger, T. (2012). GNSS jammers: how vulnerable are consumer grade satellite navigation receivers? *European Journal of Navigation*, *10*, 14-20.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/230751479_GNSS_jammers_how_vulnerable_are_consumer_grade_satellite_navigation_receivers
- Lachapelle, G., Kuusniemi, H., Dao, D. T. H., MacGougan, G., & Cannon, M. E. (2004). HSGPS Signal Analysis and Performance under Various Indoor Conditions. *NAVIGATION: Journal of the Institute of Navigation*, *51*(1), 29–43.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2161-4296.2004.tb00339.x>
- Leclère, J., Landry, R. Jr., & Botteron, C. (2018). Comparison of L1 and L5 Bands GNSS Signals Acquisition. *Sensors*, *18*(9).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/s18092779>
- Leisti, T. (Nov 2018). GPS-häirintä ulottui Lappiin Naton sotaharjoituksen aikana – häirinnästä on epäilty Venäjää. *Yle*. Retrieved 6.3.2024 from <https://yle.fi/a/3-10498891>
- Mathworks (Mar, 2024). RF Toolbox. Retrieved from <https://se.mathworks.com/help/rf/>
- Margaria, D., & Pini, M. (2015). The Spoofing Menace. In F. Doviš (Ed.), *GNSS Interference Threats and Countermeasures*. Artech House.
- Morong, T., Puričar, P., & Kovář, P. (2019). Study of the GNSS Jamming in Real Environment. *International Journal of Electronics and Telecommunications*, *65*(1), 65-70. <https://doi.org/10.24425/ijet2019.126284>
- Morrison, A., Sokolova, N., Gerrard, N., Rødningsby, A., Rost, C., & Ruotsalainen, L. (2021). RFI considerations for utility of the Galileo E6 signal. Proceedings of the 34th International Technical Meeting of the Satellite Division of The Institute of Navigation (ION GNSS 2021), <https://doi.org/10.33012/2021.18018>

- Morrison, A., Sokolova, N., Swinden, R., Musumecchi, L., & Caparra, G. (2022). *Advanced RFI Detection, Alert and Analysis System Design and Monitoring Campaign Results*. ESA. https://sintef.brage.unit.no/sintef-xmlui/bitstream/handle/11250/3046694/19_Morrison_paper-19-27-Morrison-Aiden.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Morrison, A., Sokolova, N., Solberg, A., Gerrard, N., Rødningby, A., Hauglin, H., Rødningen, T., & Dahlø, T. (2023). Jammertest 2022: Jamming and Spoofing Lessons Learned. *Engineering Proceedings*, 54(1). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/ENC2023-15445>
- Miljanovic, S., Ardizzon, F., Crosara, L., Laurenti, N., Canzian, L., Lovisotto, E., Montini, N., Pozzobon, O., & Ioannides, R. T. (2022). Experimental Testing and Impact Analysis of Jamming and Spoofing Attacks on Professional GNSS Receivers. ICL-GNSS 2022 WiP, Tampere, Finland.
- Mitch, Ryan H., Dougherty, Ryan C., Psiaki, Mark L., Powell, Steven P., O'Hanlon, Brady W., Bhatti, Jahshan A., Humphreys, Todd E. (2011). "Signal Characteristics of Civil GPS Jammers," (*ION GNSS 2011*), Portland, OR, USA, September 2011, pp. 1907-1919.
- NGA, the National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (Jan 2024). Digital Terrain elevation Data (DTED). Retrieved from <https://earth-info.nga.mil/index.php?dir=elevation&action=elevation>
- NLS, the National Land Survey of Finland (Nov 2023a). FINPOS Terms of Service. Retrieved from <https://www.maanmittauslaitos.fi/en/finpos/kayttoehdot>
- NLS (Nov 2023b). Elevation model 2 m. Retrieved from <https://www.maanmittauslaitos.fi/en/maps-and-spatial-data/datasets-and-interfaces/product-descriptions/elevation-model-2-m>
- OLRC, Office of the Law Revision Counsel (Jan 2024). The United States Code: Crimes and Criminal Procedure; Chapter 65 Malicious Mischief Sec. 1362. Retrieved from <https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?req=granuleid:USC-prelim-title18-section1362&num=0&edition=prelim>
- OSM, OpenStreetMap (Mar 2024). Copyright and License. Retrieved from <https://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>
- OS SIS ICD, Open Service Signal-in-Space Interface Control Document (Dec 2023). Signal-in-Space: Interface Control Document. Retrieved from https://www.gsc-europa.eu/sites/default/files/sites/all/files/Galileo_OS_SIS_ICD_v2.1.pdf
- Pace, P. E. (2022). *Developing Digital RF Memories and Transceiver Technologies for Electromagnetic Warfare* (1 ed.). Artech House.
- Pan, L., Zhang, X., Li, X., Li, X., Lu, C., Liu, J., & Wang, Q. (2019). Satellite availability and point positioning accuracy evaluation on a global scale for integration of GPS, GLONASS, BeiDou and Galileo. *Advances in Space Research*, 63(9), 2696-2710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2017.07.029>
- Pattinson, M., Dumville, M., Ying, Y., Fryganiotis, D., Bhuiyan, M. Z. H., Thombre, S., Kuusniemi, H., Waern, Å., Eliardsson, P., & Poloskey, M. (2017). Standardisation of GNSS threat reporting and receiver testing through international knowledge exchange, experimentation and exploitation [STRIKE3]. *European Journal of Navigation*, 15(3), 4-12.
- Paziewski, J. (2020). Recent advances and perspectives for positioning and applications with smartphone GNSS observations. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 31(9). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/ab8a7d>
- Poisel, R. A. (2014). *Electronic Warfare Receivers and Receiving Systems*. Artech House.
- Poutanen, M. (2016). *Satelliittipaikannus*. 351 p. Tähtitieteellinen yhdistys Ursa, Helsinki.
- Poutanen, M. (Apr. 2024). Land uplift. Retrieved from <https://www.maanmittauslaitos.fi/en/research/interesting-topics/land-uplift>
- Radiocommunication Act (1985). Consolidated Acts in Canada. Retrieved from <https://laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/acts/R-2/page-1.html#h-423762>

- Radio Act 1988/517. Issued in Helsinki 10.6.1988. Retrieved from https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/1988/en19880517_19920677.pdf
- Radio Mobile (Mar, 2024). About. Retrieved from <https://www.ve2dbe.com/rme.html>
- Rappaport, T. S. (1999). *Wireless Communications: Principles & Practice*. Prentice-Hall International (UK).
- RED Guide (2018). Guide to the Radio Equipment Directive 2014/53/EU. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/33162>
- RNT, The Resilient Navigation and Timing Foundation (2016). *Prioritizing Dangers to the United States from Threats to GPS –Ranking Risks and Proposed Mitigations*. Retrieved from <https://rntfnd.org/wp-content/uploads/12-7-Prioritizing-Dangers-to-US-fm-Threats-to-GPS-RNTFoundation.pdf>
- Rummukainen, A. (2023). Katkennut yhteys. *Yle*. Retrieved from <https://yle.fi/a/74-20015375>
- Saarinen, J. (2022). GPS-häirintä –Pysykö plotteri kartalla? Retrieved from <https://kipparilehti.fi/gps-hairinta-pysyko-plotteri-kartalla/>
- Salous, S. (2013). *Radio Propagation Measurement and Channel Modelling* (1 ed.). John Wiley and Sons.
- Savolainen, O., Malmivirta, T., Yan, Z., Morrison, A. & Ruotsalainen, L. (2024). Towards Jammer Fingerprinting: the Effect of the Environment and the Receiver to a Jammer Classification. [Manuscript submitted for publication].
- Seybold, J. S. (2005). *Introduction to RF Propagation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Siwiak, K. (2007). *Radiowave propagation and antennas for personal communications* (third ed.). Artech House.
- Sobot, R. (2012). *Wireless Communications Electronics: Introduction to RF Circuits and Design Techniques*. Springer.
- Spirent. (2018). GNSS: What are the default signal power levels used by PosApp for the GNSS constellations, and why are these values used? In Spirent (Ed.). Spirent Knowledge Base. Retrieved from https://support.spirent.com/SC_KnowledgeView?id=FAQ18565#_ftn1
- Subirana, J. S., Zornoza, J. M. J., & Hernandez-Pajares, M. (2011). GNSS Signal. In *ESA Navipedia*. Retrieved from https://gssc.esa.int/navipedia/index.php/GNSS_signal.
- Swider, R., Dickshinski, D., Robb, R., & Martel, J. (2000). GPS Selective Availability: A Retrospective. Proceedings of the IAIN World Congress and the 56th Annual Meeting of The Institute of Navigation (2000), San Diego.
- Söderholm, S., Bhuiyan, M. Z. H., Thombre, S., Ruotsalainen, L., & Kuusniemi, H. (2016). A multi-GNSS software-defined receiver: design, implementation, and performance benefits. *Annals of Telecommunications*, 71, 399-410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12243-016-0518-7>
- Tanghe, E., Joseph, W., Verloock, L., & Martens, L. (2008). Evaluation of Vehicle Penetration Loss at Wireless Communication Frequencies. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 57, 2036-2041.
- Thombre, S., Bhuiyan, M. Z. H., Eliardsson, P., Gabrielsson, B., Pattinson, M., Dumville, M., Fryganiotis, D., Hill, S., Manikundalam, V., Pölöskey, M., Lee, S., Ruotsalainen, L., Söderholm, S. & Kuusniemi, H. (2018). GNSS Threat Monitoring and Reporting: Past, Present, and a Proposed Future. *Journal of Navigation*, 71(3), 513–529. doi:10.1017/S0373463317000911

- Traficom (Nov 2023a). The High Accuracy Service (HAS) of the European satellite positioning system Galileo is now operational. Retrieved from <https://www.kyberturvallisuuskeskus.fi/en/news/high-accuracy-service-has-european-satellite-positioning-system-galileo-now-operational>
- Traficom (Nov 2023b). Situational picture of disturbances in satellite navigation in Finland. Retrieved from <https://www.traficom.fi/en/news/situational-picture-disturbances-satellite-navigation-finland>
- Traficom (Jan 2024). Galileo Public Regulated Service (PRS). Retrieved from <https://www.kyberturvallisuuskeskus.fi/en/our-activities/satellite-navigation/galileo-public-regulated-service-prs>
- Vogel, W. J., Torrence, G. W., & Kleiner, N. (1996). Measurement of propagation loss into cars on satellite paths at L-band. *Proceedings of the Second European Workshop on Mobile/Personal Satcoms (EMPS 96) Mobile and Personal Satellite Communications*, 129-138. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMPS.1996.864056>.
- Ward, P. W., Betz, J. W., & Hegarty, C. (2017). GNSS Disruptions. In E. D. Kaplan & C. Hegarty (Eds.), *Understanding GPS/GNSS: Principles and Applications* (Third ed.). Artech House.
- Westbrook, T. (2019). The Global Positioning System and Military Jamming: The geographies of electronic warfare. *Journal of Strategic Security*, 12(2), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.5038/1944-0472.12.2.1720>
- Yan, Z., Al-Tahmeesschi, A., Malmivirta, T., & Ruotsalainen, L. (2023). GNSS Jammer Localization in Urban Areas Based on Carrier-to-Noise Ratio and Classification Methods. *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 3434.
- Yang, B., Dong, C., Gao, B., Liu, Y., Cui, W., & Gao, F. (2022). Research on GNSS interference recognition based on ROI of correlation peaks. *International Journal of Satellite Communications and Networking*, 40(5), 330-342. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sat.1444>
- Yun, Z., & Iskander, M. F. (2015). Ray Tracing for Radio Propagation Modeling: Principles and Applications. *IEEE Access*, 3, 1089-1100. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2015.2453991>
- Xu, W., Shen, W., Cai, C., Li, L., Wang, L., Ning, A., & Shen, Z. (2022). Comparison and evaluation of carrier phase PPP and single difference time transfer with multi-GNSS ambiguity resolution. *GPS Solutions*, 26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-022-01242-2>

7 APPENDICES

Appendix 1. The code for MATLAB signal propagation. Example code for Ylläs area.

```
% Add DTED-file to path

% 1. Add the custom terrain data

dtedfile = "N67.dt2";
attribution = "Data from NLS, 2x2 m DEM";
addCustomTerrain("yllas_fell",dtedfile,"Attribution",attribution)
viewer = siteviewer("Terrain","yllas_fell");

% 2. Add the transmitter to the area

tx_mtyllas = txsite("Name","Ylläs", ...
    "Latitude",67.564113,...
    "Longitude",24.226638, ...
    "AntennaHeight", 1.5, "TransmitterFrequency", 1.5754242e9, "TransmitterPower", 1);
%power in watts

% 3. Define the propagation model

pm = propagationModel("longley-rice","TimeVariabilityTolerance",0.5); %0.5 is default
% Longley-rice propagation model can be used to calculate point-to-point
% path loss between sites over an irregular terrain (Matlab documentation)

% 4. Visualize the coverage of jamming signal
coverage(tx_mtyllas, pm, "SignalStrengths",-130:-20, MaxRange=6000); % MaxRange in
meters

% 5. Define the reference point for start point of matrix (in the area of interest)

lat_ref = 67.5611497;
lon_ref = 24.2141639;
h_ref = 579; % Exact value from NLS 2x2 m DEM, can be calculated for example by adding
transmitter to these coordinates, siteviewer tells the height

% 6. Convert reference point to ENU (Cartesian) coordinates to take the
% height into account and to create terrain data

[x_ref, y_ref, z_ref] = geodetic2enu(lat_ref, lon_ref, h_ref, lat_ref, lon_ref, h_ref,
referenceEllipsoid('grs80'));
% https://se.mathworks.com/help/map/choose-a-3-d-coordinate-system.html
% Taking the local perspective, creating the base for matrix calculations
% ETRS89 uses GRS 80 reference ellipsoid and the DTED file WGS84 system also
% has GRS 80 as its reference ellipsoid

% 7. Start the loop

% creating empty variables
total_loc_x = [];

total_loc_y = [];

% defining x and y coordinates with y_ref and x_ref
```

```

x_coor = y_ref;

y_coor = x_ref;

% defining step size, so how much is added to the value i. e. distance between
receivers; here 10m
step_size_lon = 10;
step_size_lat = 10;

%what is the difference between step sizes? The difference from the equator
%>changes in lat
%we can leave it be, because the research area is quite small

% creating borders for the area, here 1 km (100 m times step size)
x_coor_limit = 100; % in meters, need to be divisible by step size
y_coor_limit = 100; % in meters, need to be divisible by step size

% 8. The loop
for i = 0:step_size_lat:x_coor_limit
    loc_x = x_coor + step_size_lat*i;

    for j = 0:step_size_lon:y_coor_limit
        loc_y = y_coor+ step_size_lon*j;
        total_loc_x = [total_loc_x, loc_x];
        total_loc_y = [total_loc_y, loc_y];

    end
end

% loop calculates first the y-axis then down (^ >)

% variables for lats and lons combined
lats2 = total_loc_x;

lons2 = total_loc_y;

% minimum received power to detect the signal, specified as a numeric
% scalar in dBm
sens = -127.25; % the in OS SIS ICD, 2023

% number of receivers, will be 121
nof_receivers =i*j;

% creating a loop for the name of the receivers, receivers will be named rf_1, rf_2 etc
names2 = ["rf1", "rf2", "rf3", "rf4"];
full_names = [];
for n = 1:length(total_loc_x)
    names2 = sprintf("RF_%02d",n);
    full_names = [full_names, names2];

```

```
end
```

```
% 9. Convert the ENU (Cartesian) coordinates back to geodetic coordinates (so they can  
be used in rx_site function)
```

```
[x2, y2, z2] = enu2geodetic(lats2, lons2, 0, lat_ref, lon_ref, h_ref,  
referenceEllipsoid('grs80')); % change to long and lat
```

```
%10. Create receiver site with receiver matrix
```

```
rx_mtyllas = rxsite("Name",full_names,  
"Antenna",dipole,"Latitude",x2,"Longitude",y2,"ReceiverSensitivity",sens,  
"AntennaHeight", 1.5);%antennaheight of a car 1.5m
```

```
show(rx_mtyllas)
```

```
% 11. Calculate the pathloss of 121 receivers
```

```
pal1 = pathloss(pm,rx_mtyllas,tx_mtyllas);
```

```
% info about path loss
```

```
[pal1,info] = pathloss(pm, rx_mtyllas, tx_mtyllas);
```

Appendix 2. Example of a receiver matrix

Figure 21. Receiver matrix on top of Ylläs fell: here the transmitter (red dot) is situated in the middle of the matrix.

Appendix 3. DEM metadata.

Table 5. Summary of the DEM's available metadata

Area	DEM id number	Date of laser scanning	Updated in
Ylläs	U4234A	02.08.2013	2015
Seinäjäjoki	P3332G	30.06.2019	2020
Santalahti	L4343F	18.04.2021	2022
Punavuori	L4133A	07.06.2020	2021

Appendix 4. Ylläs interference over DEM limits.

Ylläs GNSS jamming scenario over DEM limits

Figure 22. Ylläs whole areas of interference. Jamming powers: A: 500 mW, B: 1 W, C: 5W, D: 40 W. It must be noted that these jamming scenarios use also the default DEM data which is not entirely accurate in elevation. The combination of NLS's DEM and default DEM provided by MATLAB are not compatible together as the visualization is not consistent.

Appendix 5. Seinäjoki interference over DEM limits

Seinäjoki GNSS jamming scenario over DEM limits

Figure 23. Seinäjoki whole areas of interference. Jamming powers: A: 500 mW, B: 1 W, C: 5W, D: 40 W. It must be noted that these jamming scenarios use also the default DEM data which is not entirely accurate in elevation. Noteworthy is that the interference propagates freely to every direction in the Alajoki expanse and the area of interference grows systematically when the transmitter power increases. Sector on the right is uncertainty of the data.

Appendix 6. Santalahti interference over DEM limits.

Santalahti GNSS jamming scenario over DEM limits

Figure 24. Santalahti whole areas of interference. Jamming powers: A: 500 mW, B: 1 W, C: 5W, D: 40 W. It must be noted that these jamming scenarios use also the default DEM data which is not entirely accurate in elevation. The vertical lines that cut the interference area in the middle parts of the pictures are the edges of NLS's DEM.